

Storage-Efficient Analysis of Spatio-Temporal Data with Application to Climate Research

Master's Thesis of

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(Andreas Weber)

Abstract

Climate research is a field where computer science is of increasing importance. This includes atmospheric science where global observations as well as model simulations provide large volumes of data. Large-scale data processing offers opportunities but also introduces challenges. This thesis focuses on atmospheric data retrieved from remote sensing satellite instruments and has two major contributions.

First, we present with adaptive low-rank matrix approximation a compression technique that reduces storage requirements through matrix factorization. Since remote sensing data as well as compression are error-prone, we propose a statistical error metric that compares the existing error in the remote sensing data with errors introduced by approximation under consideration of atmospheric properties. In contrast to general-purpose error metrics, we can estimate the practical impact for relevant applications. Together with our parameterizable implementation, we individually choose a good tradeoff between compression ratio and loss in information for each retrieved atmospheric gas. With a compression ratio adapting to the matrix structure, the average storage requirements of the given data are reduced to 42% of the original size.

Second, we apply data mining techniques to atmospheric data. The transport of water vapour is related to many atmospheric processes and its modelling belongs to major challenges in climate research. As a first step towards a data driven analysis, we compare the clustering algorithms DBSCAN and HDBSCAN with application to pairs of water vapour concentrations and its isotopologue ratios (denoted as $\{H_2O, \delta D\}$ -pairs) and their spatio-temporal context. The resulting patterns in $\{H_2O, \delta D\}$ -space are useful for further analysis, since they correlate with atmospheric processes. For a first objective quality assessment of clustered results, we compare different cluster validation indexes and discuss their validity. Judging by the validation scores and plots of subsamples, HDBSCAN outperforms DBSCAN for the given data.

Zusammenfassung

Die Klimaforschung ist ein Bereich in dem die Informatik zunehmend an Bedeutung gewinnt. Dazu gehört die Atmosphärenwissenschaft, die große Datenmengen aus Messungen und Modell-Simulationen bereitstellt. Die Verarbeitung solcher Datenmengen bietet Chancen, birgt aber auch Herausforderungen. Diese Arbeit liefert zwei wesentliche Beiträge basierend auf atmosphärischen Fernerkundungsdaten von Satelliten-Instrumenten.

Zunächst präsentieren wir mit einer adaptiven Low-Rank Approximation ein Komprimierungsverfahren, das den Speicherbedarf der Daten durch Zerlegung von Matrizen reduziert. Da sowohl die Fernerkundungsdaten also auch das Komprimierungsverfahren fehlerbehaftet sind, stellen wir eine statistische Fehlermetrik vor, die den vorhandenen Fehler mit dem Approximationsfehler unter Berücksichtigung von atmosphärischen Eigenschaften vergleicht. Dadurch können im Gegensatz zu allgemeinen Fehlermetriken die praktischen Auswirkungen des Fehlers für relevante Anwendungen besser abgeschätzt werden. In Kombination mit einer parametrisierbaren Implementierung erlaubt das Verfahren einen guten Kompromiss zwischen Kompressionsverhältnis und Informationsverlust für jedes betrachtete atmosphärische Gas zu bestimmen. Durch die Anpassung des Kompressionsverhältnisses an die Matrixstruktur reduziert sich der durchschnittliche Speicherbedarf der gegebenen Daten insgesamt auf 42% der ursprünglichen Größe.

Darüber hinaus wenden wir Data-Mining Techniken auf den atmosphärischen Daten an. Der Transport von Wasserdampf hängt mit vielen atmosphärischen Prozessen zusammen und dessen Modellierung gehört zu den großen Herausforderungen in der Klimaforschung. Als ersten Schritt einer datengetriebenen Analyse vergleichen wir die Clustering-Algorithmen DBSCAN und HDBSCAN anhand von Paaren aus Wasserdampfkonzentrationen und dessen Isotopologenverhältnisse (bezeichnet als $\{H_2O, \delta D\}$ -Paare) unter Berücksichtigung ihres räumlich-zeitlichen Kontextes. Die resultierenden Muster im $\{H_2O, \delta D\}$ -Raum sind für die weitere Analyse nützlich, da sie mit atmosphärischen Prozessen korrelieren. Für eine erste objektive Bewertung der Cluster-Ergebnisse vergleichen wir verschiedene Cluster-Validierungsmetriken und diskutieren deren Eignung. HDBSCAN übertrifft DBSCAN für die gegebenen Daten sowohl nach Validierungsmetriken als auch visueller Bewertung.

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1. Introduction

This thesis is part of the project MOTIV (MOisture Transport and Isotopologues of water Vapour) that aims on a better understanding of atmospheric processes related to water vapour. Due to the interdependency of water with cloud formations, heat transport and radiation, tracking these processes is of great interest as well as a main challenge in climate research [1]. Therefore, we try to discover spatial and temporal coincidences as well as patterns in atmospheric data that can be matched to such climatological processes.

1.1. Motivation for Compression

Climate research is a scientific field that increasingly involves massive amounts of data. According to estimates, the volume of climate data reached at least 10 Petabytes in 2010. Over the last years, the volume further increased and is expected to grow exponentially. The different types of climate data can be categorized by their sources which are among others in-situ, remote sensed, model output and paleoclimatic data [2]. The project MOTIV founds on the remotely sensed retrievals of IASI instruments, which are mounted on MetOp satellites and operated by the European Organisation for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites (EUMETSAT).

The general growth of climate data also applies to measurements performed by the IASI instruments: One instrument daily performs around 1.3 million measurements. The first satellite MetOp-A was launched in 2006, the second MetOp-B in 2012, and the third MetOp-C in 2018 [3]. Therefore, the data volume constantly increased in last decade. Persistence of the atmospheric state in our dataset requires around 93 KB¹ of storage per individual observation. Summed up, this results in a data volume of 121 GB per day per satellite. Under the assumption that all measurements are processed, the current storage requirements of atmospheric state are above 10 TB for three satellites and 30 days. But in fact, the real volume is often smaller because some observations are excluded from the analysis (e.g. for a focus on cloud free conditions, approximately 65% of all observations are excluded).

Because of the healthy state of MetOp-A and -B satellites, EUMETSAT decided to extend their lifetime to 2027 [4]. In the future, the data volume is going to increase even further: the launch of the second generation satellite MetOp-SG A1 is planned for 2023. This satellite will be equipped with the next generation IASI instrument – IASI-NG – which provides among other advances a higher vertical resolution. Until 2036 at least two other MetOp launches with IASI-NG instruments are planned [5, 6].

Even today, the storage requirements of the last years including only measurements of MetOp-A and -B are already very demanding. If the period of analysis includes multiple

¹Average observation size is based on the samples provided in Table 3.2

months, a computer centre with large storage facilities is needed to handle this amount of data. Here, even semi-efficient compression can significantly reduce the absolute storage requirements and costs due to the huge amounts of data.

Besides the plain storage requirements of atmospheric data, there is another drawback of such a huge data volume: the transmission and exchange of data. As an internationally oriented project, we aim to make processed data accessible to the scientific community. Because the processing of IASI measurements is computation-intensive and needs thousands of CPU hours, it is not practicable that all involved institutions process IASI measurements again. Instead, IASI measurements are processed once at the supercomputers ForHLR I and ForHLR II² from KIT and results are shared with cooperating institutions. Consequentially, the processed data leaves the data center with internal highspeed network connections. Here, the given options are transmitting via internet or shipping of physical volumes like hard drives or computer tapes. Both procedures are time-consuming and benefit from a reduced data volume.

1.2. Motivation for Analysis

Data mining, as a data driven approach, has increasing popularity in several scientific fields including climate research. Even if data mining involves unique challenges in climate research, several methods have been established to analyse climate data [2]. One subfield of data mining is spatio-temporal clustering that aims to group data with respect to their spatial and temporal similarity. Climate research is one, but not the only application of spatio-temporal analysis. For example with the arise of location sensors in mobile devices, there are several datasets that are associated with a spatio-temporal context [7].

With the given IASI retrievals, we have observations with global extent over multiple years. To exploit the potential of such a large-scale dataset, spatio-temporal clustering as a data driven approach is helpful for a better understanding of atmospheric processes related to water vapour. Related work shows that characteristic distributions of water vapour and its isotopologues ratio denoted as $\{H_2O, \delta D\}$ -pairs correlate with different atmospheric processes [8]. Aggregated clusters could establish a new form of analysis that reveals patterns in $\{H_2O, \delta D\}$ -space, extracts cluster properties and compares their spatial and temporal changes and coherences.

A major challenge in cluster analysis is validation [9, 10]. Since the ground truth of underlying atmospheric processes is unknown, a measure is needed to assess the clustered results. Various cluster validation indexes have been established to give an objective and quantitative measure for cluster quality.

As a first step towards a better understanding of atmospheric processes, we compare the quality of clustering algorithms and the validity of cluster indexes to optimize spatio-temporal clustering in the domain of atmospheric data.

²Forschungshocheistungrechner I & II <https://www.scc.kit.edu/dienste/forh1r.php>

2. Background

In the following sections, we cover the fundamentals of the project. These include the atmospheric measurements of the satellite instrument, the retrieval of the atmospheric gas concentrations as well as the role of water vapour for climatological processes.

2.1. Infrared Atmospheric Sounding Interferometer

In climate research there are different ways to detect the composition of the atmosphere. Besides different measurement techniques (in-situ and remote) there are different platforms including ground stations, airplanes and weather balloons. However, these platforms are insufficient to achieve global coverage. This is why remote sensing with satellites has been established in the last decades: it provides a global coverage with simultaneous good quality of data [2].

One operational remote sensing instrument is the Infrared Atmospheric Sounding Interferometer (IASI) mounted on MetOp satellites. The satellites are positioned on polar orbits in an altitude of 817 km [3]. With 14 orbits a day, a satellite provides measurements on global scale twice a day [11]. On its orbit, the IASI continuously measures across track with a swath width around 2.200 km [11]. One of those measurement lines contains 30 views with 2×2 instantaneous fields of view respectively (see Figure 2.1) [12]. Given these fields of view, one IASI instrument performs in total about 1.3 million measurements per day.

As a remote sensing instrument, the IASI does not measure gas concentrations directly. Instead, it measures the infrared part of the electromagnetic spectrum emitted by the earth's surface and emitted and absorbed by the atmosphere [11]. The spectra are influenced by many factors: these include, among others, the gas concentrations in the atmosphere, the type of surface (e.g. sea, ice, forest, desert), surface temperature and clouds. On the one hand, we can derive environmental conditions from the spectra. On the other hand, those factors introduce uncertainties about the real atmospheric state.

Figure 2.1.: Field of view of IASI instrument [11]

2.2. MUSICA IASI Algorithm

The MUSICA IASI algorithm is used to derive the atmospheric state from IASI measurements – also known as retrieval [13, 14, 15]. To retrieve the atmospheric state for various gas concentrations, the algorithm requires several inputs. These include the EUMETSAT Level 1 and Level 2 data with the spectra of the IASI instrument as well as further information about the condition at time and location of measurement, e.g. surface emissivity, flags for cloud conditions, surface type, etc. [12]. Furthermore, the algorithm uses for the retrieval of the atmospheric state the spectroscopic database HITRAN2016 (Gorden et al. [16]) and topographic data from GTOPO30 developed by the US Geological Survey and provided by the Oak Ridge National Laboratory Distributed Active Archive Center (ORNL DAAC). The computation, based on the PROFFIT-nadir implementation by Hase et al. [17], is time consuming due to its complexity.

The retrieved atmospheric state includes concentrations of gases as well as temperature. While concentrations are given in parts per million by volume (ppmv), temperature is given in Kelvin (K). Because concentrations and temperatures are varying in different altitudes, the retrieved values are discretized into multiple number of levels. Depending on the topography at the location of measurement, the number of levels is 28 above sea surfaces and decreases above mountains (it can even reach a maximum of 29 in the rare case of geological depressions).

The most essential variable for atmospheric state is the result profile \hat{x} – a vector quantifying the gas concentrations (or temperature) for each atmospheric level. For most applications the result profile alone is not sufficient. In addition, the averaging kernel and the used a priori information are required for a correct interpretation of remote sensing data products. The result profile \hat{x} , the used a priori profile x_a , the averaging kernel A , the real atmospheric profile x and errors Δx are related as follows [18]:

$$(\hat{x} - x_a) = A(x - x_a) + \Delta x \quad (2.1)$$

- **A priori profile** (x_a) is a vector representing a priori knowledge about the atmospheric state. This may include typical temperature profiles at a given time and location or a characteristic distribution of a gas. The retrieval updates the a priori knowledge by exploiting the information in the measured spectra, i.e. in a strict sense the difference between the real and the a priori state is the quantity determined by the retrieval process. Because in general not all details of this difference can be captured by the retrieval, the retrieval result is dependent on the used a priori information. This has to be considered for data application.
- **Averaging kernel** (A) is a matrix indicating to which degree the retrieved gas concentrations at a level are influenced by the used a priori. In a perfect world, the matrix would be the identity matrix, meaning the retrieval can detect all the details of the difference between the real and the a priori atmospheric state. In reality, kernels are "smeared" identity matrices. Figure 2.2a depicts typical averaging kernels.
- **Cross averaging kernel with atmospheric temperature** ($A_{T_{atm}}$) has a similar function like averaging kernel but describes the cross dependence between the retrieved gas and the atmospheric a priori data. Each entry in the matrix indicates to which degree the atmospheric temperature a priori influences the retrieved gas concentration for the given level.
- **Cross averaging kernel with surface temperature** works analogously to atmospheric temperature cross kernel but describes the dependence of retrieved trace gas on the surface temperature a priori. Since the surface temperature is single valued, this kernel is rather a vector than a matrix.
- **Noise matrix** (N) is a covariance matrix indicating the uncertainty introduced by the measurement noise of the IASI instrument.

A kernel matrix informs about vertical resolution and response of the remote sensing data product. First, vertical resolution is a measure of the kernels' vertical extent over altitudes. A poor vertical resolution means that the retrieved concentration is influenced by concentrations at faraway levels. Vice versa, a high vertical resolution indicates that only nearby altitudes affect the retrieved concentration. Second, the missing response is a quality measure for the completeness of a kernel similar to a damping coefficient: If the sum of a kernel row is near one, the missing response for that level is low. In the following, the term good sensitivity refers to high vertical resolution and response and the term poor sensitivity refers to low vertical resolution and response respectively.

The gas concentrations retrieved by the MUSICA IASI algorithm include the different water vapour isotopologues H_2O (representing $H_2^{16}O$, $H_2^{17}O$, $H_2^{18}O$) and HDO (representing $HD^{16}O$), greenhouse gases N_2O and CH_4 , as well as nitric acid HNO_3 . Because tropospheric gas concentrations are well described by a log normal distribution, they are processed by

2. Background

Figure 2.2.: Matrices related to water vapour

the MUSICA IASI algorithm in log scale [18], e.g. we denote the state of water vapour with $\{\ln[H_2O], \ln[HDO]\}$. Compared to nitric acid, water vapour and greenhouse gases include two chemical compounds which results in four kernel matrices instead of one: two matrices respectively model the dependence of the same compound and two matrices respectively model the cross dependence to the other compound. Figure 2.2a illustrates the relation of the water vapour averaging kernel matrices: "The upper left graph documents the altitude regions of real atmospheric $\ln[H_2O]$ variations that affect retrieved $\ln[H_2O]$, the upper right graph the altitudes of real atmospheric $\ln[HDO]$ variations that affect retrieved $\ln[H_2O]$, the lower left graph the altitudes of real atmospheric $\ln[H_2O]$ that affect retrieved $\ln[HDO]$ and the lower right graph the altitude regions of real atmospheric $\ln[HDO]$ that affect retrieved $\ln[HDO]$, respectively." [18] Analogous, there are two cross averaging kernels of $\ln[H_2O]$ respectively $\ln[HDO]$ with atmospheric temperature (see Figure 2.2c). In total, the atmospheric state of water vapour and greenhouse gases includes respectively ten matrices, while measurements of nitric acid include only three matrices.

In the context of the project MOTIV, the concentrations of greenhouse gases and nitric acid are not considered since the analysis is based on water vapour. However, their retrievals may be used in other projects.

2.3. Water Vapour and Climatological Processes

Concentrations of water isotopologues are a promising foundation for a better understanding of climatological processes. In this context, the isotopologue ratio of water vapour is of special interest. This ratio is typically expressed by the δD -notation

$$\delta D = 1000\text{‰} \times \left(\frac{HDO/H_2O}{SMOW} - 1 \right) \quad (2.2)$$

where $SMOW = 3.1152 \times 10^{-4}$ (standard mean ocean water) [18]. The δD value indicates the deviation of the HDO/H_2O ratio compared to the mean isotopologue ratio of ocean water. Noone et al. examined the role of water isotopologues in relation to atmospheric processes [8]. They match given concentrations of $\{H_2O, \delta D\}$ with atmospheric processes such as drying by mixing or by condensation and rainout. In a coordinate system spanned by the concentrations of H_2O and δD , they depict δD as a function of H_2O . For the resulting curves, they observe a coherence between the course of the curve and the underlying process. For spatio-temporal analysis in Chapter 4, we are looking for such patterns in $\{H_2O, \delta D\}$ -space that are similar to such characteristic curves and could be matched to climatological processes.

Water vapour isotopologues $\{H_2O, HDO\}$ have some special properties that make their retrieval non-trivial. This thesis uses the proposed solution by Schneider et al. [18] that is summarized in the two sections below.

2.3.1. Representation of Water Isotopologues

Water isotopologues $\{H_2O, HDO\}$ are highly correlated due to their chemical similarity even if the abundancy of HDO is significantly lower. We are rather interested in the isotopologue ratio (denoted as δD , Equation 2.2) than in HDO concentrations because δD is less correlated to H_2O and has a stronger relation to climatological processes. Since concentrations of H_2O and HDO are given in logarithmic scale, the isotopic ratio can be approximated by the difference of their logarithms:

$$\delta D \approx \ln[HDO/H_2O] = \ln[HDO] - \ln[H_2O] \quad (2.3)$$

For convenience, we introduce $\{\ln[H_2O], \delta D\}$ as a proxy state that is found on an orthogonal transform expressed by the transformation matrix

$$P = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{2}\mathbb{I} & \frac{1}{2}\mathbb{I} \\ -\mathbb{I} & \mathbb{I} \end{pmatrix} \quad (2.4)$$

The lower rows of P build the difference of the logarithms ($\ln[H_2O] - \ln[HDO]$) as given by Equation 2.3. In contrast, the upper rows build the normalized sum of the logarithms $(\ln[H_2O] + \ln[HDO])/2$. Since $\ln[H_2O]$ and $\ln[HDO]$ are highly correlated,

their normalized sum is still an appropriate measure of humidity (or $\ln[H_2O]$). Given the transformation matrix P , an averaging kernel of water vapour A_{WV} can be transformed from the state $\{\ln[H_2O], \ln[HDO]\}$ to the proxy state $\{\ln[H_2O], \delta D\}$ by

$$A'_{WV} = PA_{WV}P^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} A'_{HH} & A'_{IH} \\ A'_{HI} & A'_{II} \end{pmatrix} \quad (2.5)$$

where A'_{WV} is also denoted as the kernel of the type 1 product. Here, the upper left humidity kernel A'_{HH} indicates to which extent the real atmospheric variations of the humidity proxy ($\{(\ln[H_2O] + \ln[HDO])/2\}$) affect the retrieved humidity proxy values. Analogously, the lower right isotopologue ratio kernel A'_{II} indicates to which extent the real atmospheric variations of the δD proxy ($\{\ln[HDO] - \ln[H_2O]\}$) affect the retrieved δD proxy values. Because H_2O and δD are loosely correlated, the lower left kernel A'_{HI} and the upper right kernel A'_{IH} are low valued in contrast to the averaging kernels representing the $\{\ln[H_2O], \ln[HDO]\}$ state (the kernels depicted in Figure 2.2a). In the following, we use the $\{H_2O, \delta D\}$ proxy state as an alias for $\{\ln[H_2O], \delta D\}$ (i.e. we do not explicitly mention the logarithmic scale).

2.3.2. Representation of $\{H_2O, \delta D\}$ -Pairs

Since H_2O and HDO are highly correlated, their ratio δD is relatively invariable in contrast to the humidity H_2O . As a consequence, the sensitivity of the isotopologue ratio kernel A'_{II} is worse than the sensitivity of humidity kernel A'_{HH} . A diverging sensitivity implies that the kernels are modeling contributions of different air masses. For a meaningful analysis of $\{H_2O, \delta D\}$ and their interpretability, this circumstance is insufficient. As a solution, the sensitivity of the kernels is adapted by the correction matrix

$$C = \begin{pmatrix} A'_{II} & 0 \\ -A'_{HI} & \mathbb{I} \end{pmatrix} \quad (2.6)$$

also denoted as the a posteriori transformation matrix. The a posteriori transformation of the kernel A'_{WV} is defined as

$$A''_{WV} = CA'_{WV} \quad (2.7)$$

and is also denoted as the averaging kernel of the type 2 product. Here, the sensitivity of the humidity kernel in A''_{WV} is adapted to the poorer sensitivity of the δD kernel, which improves interpretability because now both kernels are sensitive to the same air mass. Furthermore, the a posteriori transformation reduces the cross dependence of retrieved δD on atmospheric humidity variations [18].

2.4. Summary

Figure 2.3 outlines the main processing steps in context of the project MOTIV as well as the subjects of this thesis: Based on the IASI measurements and information about spectroscopy, surface emissivity and topography, the MUSICA IASI algorithm is able to retrieve the atmospheric state of water vapour (H_2O , HDO), greenhouse gases (N_2O , CH_4) and nitric acid (HNO_3). Due to the large-scale volume of the data, low-rank matrix approximation is evaluated in Chapter 3 to improve the storage efficiency and to facilitate the exchange with the scientific community. In Chapter 4, we evaluate clustering algorithms to find patterns in $\{H_2O, \delta D\}$ -space with respect to their spatio-temporal context. This analysis is based on the a posteriori optimized water vapour retrievals that provide a better interpretability than the unadjusted retrievals.

Although this thesis focusses on the application to climate research, the contributions to low-rank matrix approximation and spatio-temporal clustering are of general interest because both techniques can also be applied to datasets in other domains.

Figure 2.3.: Overview of the processing steps in the MOTIV project. The highlighted boxes are main topics covered in this thesis.

3. Storage Efficiency

In this chapter, we present our approach to improve the storage efficiency of atmospheric data. Based on a description of data characteristics, we review work related to compression of matrices. In Section 3.3, we introduce with adaptive low-rank matrix approximation our approach to reduce the size of matrices. Due to the lossy nature of approximation, we present a domain specific error metric that compares existing error in data with error introduced by approximation under consideration of a priori knowledge about the atmosphere. With that, we are able to estimate the error for different compression ratios. Finally, we show in a use case that the loss in information is negligible for the application of the data.

3.1. Data Description

The atmospheric state is defined by multiple variables as described in Section 2.2. These include state vectors, averaging kernels and noise matrices but also meta information of given retrievals like time, location, altitude or flags. Due to the higher dimensionality, the data volume is dominated by averaging kernels and noise matrices, while meta data as well as state vectors are negligible relating to storage requirements. This is why we focus on methods for matrix compression.

Figure 2.2 visualizes the different types of matrices related to water vapour. Instead of being randomly distributed, the matrix values are continuous and their structures are similar to each other. For example the noise of water vapour depicted by Figure 2.2b appears to be the same for all quadrants but in fact there are small differences. Another observation is that higher absolute values are concentrated at the diagonal of the matrices. To the contrary, values outside the diagonal tend to be zero-valued. The matrices are not sparse because values are only near zero – not exactly zero. This is reasonable because the matrices are modeling the mutual impact of atmospheric levels and the adjacent levels have the biggest impact. The same applies to the noise matrices with the addition that they are as covariance matrices per definition symmetric and accordingly contain redundant information.

3.2. Related Work

There are several methods that aim to reduce the size of similar structured data. Compression of data is in general either lossy or lossless. This section provides an overview of compression techniques that can be applied to matrices.

3.2.1. Lossless Compression Methods

Many general-purpose compression algorithms are lossless, e.g. the popular deflate method that is used in well established software like Zip and Gzip. Its applications range from the HTTP protocol, via the PNG photo format through to the NetCDF file format (see Section 3.4.1). The algorithm belongs to the category of dictionary-based compression methods which achieve size reduction by replacing repetitive subsequences with a reference to a dictionary [19, 20].

An area more specialized to matrices is sparse matrix compression. For sparse matrices with many zero values there are alternative matrix representations that are not only more compact but also may be more efficient for some matrix operations. These representations include among others Compressed Sparse Column (CSC), Compressed Sparse Row (CSR) and Dictionary of Keys (DOK) [21]. Unfortunately, these representations are not appropriate because the given matrices are not strictly sparse as stated above.

In general, the compression factor of lossless methods is expected to be lower, because the continuous value range is expected to have less frequent patterns at bit level except for invalid measurements, where matrices contain fill values. With *fpzip* there exists a lossless compression method that is specialized on floating points and uses predictive coding. Its authors have shown that *fpzip* achieves a better compression ratio than *zlib* in their benchmarks [22].

3.2.2. Lossy Compression Methods

Lossy compression is appropriate if a small loss in information is acceptable. Since measurements by the IASI instruments are error-prone, small errors in compression are acceptable as long as they are negligible compared to the original error. Due to a normally better compression ratio, lossy compression is a good option in many domains. Baker et al. review lossy compression methods on climate simulation data and use a measure of pointwise error, average error and correlation to evaluate the results [23]. The analysed algorithms include among others a lossy variant of *fpzip*, where least significant bits are truncated, as well as an algorithm based on wavelet compression in JPEG 2000. The latter approach has also been evaluated by Woodring et al. to reduce the size of simulation data in the context of climate research [24].

When it comes to lossy compression of matrices, low-rank matrix approximation is a popular approach, e.g. with application to images. Rehna et al. use low-rank singular value decomposition (SVD) to approximate respective RGB channels of pictures [25]. Hou et al. take a more extended approach: they introduce sparse low-rank matrix approximation exploiting both intra coherence (structure within a matrix) and inter coherence (redundant information among various samples) [26]. Besides image sets, they also evaluate the proposed compression technique on dynamic 3D meshes, where the cartesian coordinates are represented by three matrices respectively containing the position of m vertices and n frames.

Velagar et al. evaluate matrix approximation in context of atmospheric chemistry [27]. They also exploit the inter coherence of samples by summarizing multiple dimensions in a single matrix. These include longitude, latitude, elevation and time of simulation

state. Due to the size of the resulting matrix, a more efficient randomized variant of SVD, presented by Halko et al. [28], is used. In preprocessing, they address some problems specific to atmospheric data: First, concentrations of chemicals are highly variable. To prevent SVD from neglecting low values, they represent concentrations on logarithmic scale. Second, they expect that translational and rotational invariants in low-rank features are not well covered by SVD. Thus, they align data in a consistent manner e.g. by shifting the concentrations of chemicals from global Coordinated Universal Time to local time. With that, the variations in concentrations dependent on daytime – like a daily peak at noon – are independent of location. In general, the authors motivate low-rank matrix approximation not only with a more compact representation of simulation results, but also with a more efficient analysis through reduction in dimensionality. Because concentrations of chemicals are positive, the authors enforce positive valued factors by using Nonnegative Matrix Factorization (NMF). The preserved positivity as well as sparsity support a better interpretability of factorized matrices in a physical meaningful sense.

3.2.3. Applications of Singular Value Decomposition

The applications of singular value decomposition (SVD) are not limited to low-rank matrix approximation. Before we start a detailed discussion of SVD in context of matrix approximation, we survey other applications of SVD.

One well-known application of SVD is the Principal Components Analysis (PCA). PCA is motivated with a dimensionality reduction in data analysis. The notion is that a dataset with multiple features can be explained with a smaller set of features known as principal components [29]. Here, the linear dependence between features is used to reduce the dimensions. The stronger features are correlated, the more efficient is the reduction. Principal components of a $n \times d$ data set X containing n samples and d features can be calculated with both SVD and eigen decomposition of the covariance matrix of X [30, 31].

More generally speaking, SVD provides a solution for the least square problem. For example, SVD can be used to construct the pseudo-inverse. The pseudo-inverse provides the best solution (in a least square sense) of an overdetermined system of linear equations $Ax = b$ – a relevant problem in several domains [29, 32].

Another application of SVD is the implementation of recommendation systems; e.g. in context of a Netflix movie recommendation challenge, SVD has been used to predict missing ratings in a matrix of movie ratings by users [33]. The idea behind this approach is that SVD reveals the typical ratings of similar user groups such that a predicted rating indicates the user's preference for the movie [34]. Similar applications are depicted by a blog post of Facebook Research like hashtag recommendation based on their co-occurrence with post content [35]. Here, they benchmark the more performant randomized SVD by Halko et al. [28] due to large-scale of data in depicted scenario.

3.3. Low-Rank Matrix Approximation

The notion of low-rank matrix approximation is the reduction of the matrix rank without significant loss in information. More formally, low-rank matrix approximation aims to

construct a matrix M' of lower rank than the original matrix M such that $M' \approx M$. Rank reduction is achieved by exploiting the fact that the structure of many matrices contains linear dependencies – like our matrices described above – such that an approximation is possible with fewer linear combinations.

In 1936, Eckart and Young proposed a solution to low-rank matrix approximation [36]. With contributions by Mirsky [37], the so called Eckart-Young-Mirsky theorem provides an optimal low-rank approximation with respect to the Frobenius norm. Nowadays, this solution is known as singular value decomposition [38].

In contrast to the proposed method by Velagar et al. [27], we factorize matrices per measurement. As a main drawback, singular value decomposition cannot exploit linear dependencies between measurements such that the compression ratio is limited. In return, measurements are non-interacting e.g. due to variances in geographic location. Furthermore, the number of levels is varying with measurements such that measurements cannot be grouped into one matrix without filling values. With that, our approach integrates better in the existing data layout and allows straightforward access to subsamples.

3.3.1. Mathematical Basics

For a better understanding of the following sections, we recap some mathematical basics.

3.3.1.1. Matrix Rank

The rank r of a $m \times n$ matrix M denoted as

$$r = \rho(M) \tag{3.1}$$

corresponds to the number of linear independent rows or columns of M , where $r \leq \min(m, n)$ [31].

3.3.1.2. Orthogonal Matrix

“An $n \times n$ square matrix M is called orthogonal if its columns (or rows) are orthonormal vectors (i.e., orthogonal vectors of unit length)” [31]. Equivalently, an orthogonal matrix satisfies the constraint

$$M^T M = M M^T = \mathbb{I} \Leftrightarrow M^T = M^{-1} \tag{3.2}$$

3.3.1.3. Eigenvalues, Eigenvectors and Singular Values

Matrices can be used for linear transformation of vectors. Normally, multiplication of a vector v with matrix M results in a vector v' with a different direction, but there are special vectors where v and v' have the same direction. For a square matrix M , a nonzero vector v which satisfies the constraint

$$Mv = \lambda v \tag{3.3}$$

is called (right) eigenvector of M and the scalar λ the corresponding eigenvalue [31, 39]. Together, (λ, v) are denoted as an eigenpair of M . Vice versa, v is a left singular vector of M if

$$v^T M = \lambda v^T \quad (3.4)$$

as defined by Banerjee et al. [31]. The relation between eigenvalues and singular values is as follows: Let M be a rectangular $m \times n$ matrix. Then singular values of M are the square roots of the eigenvalues of the symmetric matrix $M^T M$ [39]. Singular values are calculated by singular value decomposition and have some special properties e.g. in Frobenius norm below.

3.3.1.4. Frobenius Norm

For a $m \times n$ matrix A , the Frobenius norm is defined as

$$\|A\|_F = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n |a_{i,j}|^2} = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^{\min(m,n)} \sigma_i^2(A)} \quad (3.5)$$

where $\sigma_i(A)$ are singular values of A [29, 32].

3.3.1.5. Positive Semi-Definite Matrix

A symmetric $n \times n$ matrix M that satisfies the constraint

$$\forall x \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus \{0\} : x^T M x \geq 0 \quad (3.6)$$

is called positive semi-definite or nonnegative definite [31].

3.3.1.6. Covariance

For two jointly distributed random vectors $x = (x_1, \dots, x_n)$ and $y = (y_1, \dots, y_n)$ their sample covariance is defined as

$$\text{cov}(x, y) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{n - 1} \quad (3.7)$$

where \bar{x} and \bar{y} are respectively the vector mean. A positive covariance indicates that greater values in x tend to correspond with greater values in y and lower values in x tend to correspond with lower values in y . In contrast, a negative covariance indicates that greater values of one variable tend to correspond with lower values of the other and vice versa. Two variables x, y are uncorrelated iff $\text{cov}(x, y) = 0$ [29, 40]. The covariance of the same variable $\text{cov}(x, x)$ is denoted as the variance of x . Equation 3.7 reveals that the variance of x is equal to its squared standard deviation.

Covariance matrices represent the covariance of multiple variables. Let X be a $n \times d$ matrix with d variables and n samples. The sample covariance matrix of X is a $d \times d$ matrix S defined as

$$S = \frac{1}{n-1}(X - \mu)^T(X - \mu) = (\text{cov}(C_i, C_j)) \quad (3.8)$$

where $\mu = (\mu_1, \dots, \mu_d)$ with μ_j is the mean of the j -th column C_j of X and $X - \mu$ are centered rows with $X_i - \mu$ for $1 \leq i \leq n$ [29]. The value S_{ij} represents the covariance between the i -th and the j -th variable. Because $\text{cov}(x, y) = \text{cov}(y, x)$, a covariance matrix is symmetric. More specifically, covariance matrices are positive semi-definite [31]. The diagonal entries of S quantify the variance of their respective variables.

3.3.2. Eigen Decomposition

Eigen decomposition, also known as spectral decomposition, is the factorization of a matrix by its eigenvalues and eigenvectors. It is based on the so-called spectral theorem stating: “If M is a real symmetric $n \times n$ matrix, then there exists an orthogonal matrix V and a real diagonal matrix Λ such that

$$V^T M V = \Lambda. \quad (3.9)$$

The diagonal entries of Λ are the eigenvalues of M and the columns of V are the corresponding eigenvectors.” [31]. Depending on the rank r of M , the number of nonzero eigenvalues λ_i varies because $\lambda_1 \geq \lambda_2 \geq \dots \geq \lambda_r$ and $\lambda_i = 0$ for $i = r + 1, r + 2, \dots, n$ [31]. Based on the definition of an eigenpair (λ, v) , we can extend Equation 3.3 to all eigenpairs (Λ, V) of M and observe the equality with the spectral theorem in Equation 3.9 [31]:

$$\begin{aligned} Mv &= \lambda v \\ MV &= V\Lambda \\ V^T M V &= \Lambda \\ M &= V\Lambda V^T = ED(M) \end{aligned} \quad (3.10)$$

Note that the equations can be rearranged because V is orthogonal. As a result, M is represented as a product of its eigenvalues and eigenvectors.

With the eigen decomposition, we have an alternative representation of a symmetric matrix that is beneficial to decrease the rank (and size) of the matrix with a small loss in information: The original structure of the matrix is now represented by its eigenvectors. Recap that V is orthogonal and thus its eigenvectors are unit length. In a geometric space an eigenvector only represents the direction – not a characteristic length. Analogously, eigenvectors encode a part of the original matrix structure but not the degree of contribution to the original matrix. The latter describes the role of the eigenvalues: they are scaling factors that weight the contribution of an eigenvector. Using this fact, we are able to reduce the rank of M by selecting only eigenpairs with great eigenvalues and denote the reconstructed matrix as a result of truncated eigen decomposition:

$$M_{rc} = V_{n \times k} \Lambda_{k \times k} V_{k \times n}^T = ED_k(M) \quad (3.11)$$

In this equation $k \leq n$ denotes the target rank of the approximated matrix. That arises the question of an appropriate target rank for truncated eigen decomposition. As a first constraint, k should be selected such that

$$k < \frac{n^2}{n+1} \quad (3.12)$$

because this is the bound where the truncated eigen decomposition has less numbers than the original $n \times n$ matrix. As a second constraint, k should not be too low because of the loss in information. One straightforward approach is to perform ED_k with different target ranks, measure the loss in information with a meaningful error metric and select k as best tradeoff between size reduction and error.

In context of atmospheric state, we assume that the variability in the degree of information, modeled by noise matrices, depends on different factors. These include the type of gas as well as the different contexts of measurement. To address this variability, we use a heuristic to determine an adaptive target rank that is parameterizable with a threshold $\epsilon < 1$:

$$\Lambda_k = \{\lambda_i \in \Lambda \mid \lambda_i > \epsilon \lambda_1 \wedge \lambda_i > 0\} \quad (3.13)$$

The heuristic selects the k greatest eigenvalues, where k depends on the ratio of λ_1/λ_k with respect to ϵ . The lower the threshold ϵ , the higher the target rank k . The ratio is also known as the condition number that can be used to estimate the error of a perturbation [32].

3.3.3. Singular Value Decomposition

Eigen decomposition, as defined in Section 3.3.2, works well for symmetric matrices. This qualifies the factorization method for noise matrices. With asymmetric matrices like (cross) averaging kernels, eigen decomposition is not possible. Instead, we use singular value decomposition (SVD) as a generalization of eigen decomposition that works with arbitrary rectangular matrices.

Let M be a real rectangular $m \times n$ matrix of rank r . The singular value decomposition of M is defined as

$$M = U_{m \times m} \Sigma_{m \times n} V_{n \times n}^T = SVD(M) \quad (3.14)$$

where Σ is a diagonal matrix with singular values σ_i of M at diagonal positions i and $\sigma_1 \geq \sigma_2 \geq \dots \geq \sigma_{\min(m,n)} \geq 0$. U and V are orthogonal matrices whose columns are called left- respectively right-singular vectors of M [31].

The singular value decomposition is closely related to eigen decomposition: For each $m \times n$ matrix a symmetric matrix MM^T can be constructed. Following the spectral theorem in Equation 3.9 and the definition of SVD in Equation 3.14, a matrix multiplied with its transpose is equal to

$$MM^T = U \Sigma V^T V \Sigma^T U^T = U \Sigma \Sigma^T U^T = U \Lambda U^T \quad (3.15)$$

Figure 3.1.: Size reduction with truncated singular value decomposition of a $m \times n$ matrix with target rank $k = 3$.

where $\Lambda = \Sigma \Sigma^T$ because singular values are square roots of eigenvalues (see Section 3.3.1.3). Therefore, left-singular vectors U of M are eigenvectors of MM^T . Analogous to Equation 3.15, it can be shown that the right-singular vectors V correspond to the eigenvectors of $M^T M$, while the singular values in Σ are the square roots of nonzero eigenvalues of both MM^T and $M^T M$. The rank r of M is equal to the number of strictly positive singular values of Σ such that the diagonal entries can be written as $\sigma_1 \geq \sigma_2 \geq \dots \geq \sigma_r > 0$. By implication, the number of zero singular values is equal to $\min(m, n) - r$ [31].

Analogous to the eigen decomposition, we define a truncated version of singular value decomposition SVD_k with target rank k as

$$M_{rc} = U_{m \times k} \Sigma_{k \times k} V_{k \times n}^T = SVD_k(M) \quad (3.16)$$

The target rank k of SVD_k also depends on the condition number σ_1/σ_k with respect to the threshold $\epsilon < 1$:

$$\Sigma_k = \{\sigma_i \in \Sigma | \sigma_i > \epsilon \sigma_1\} \quad (3.17)$$

The resulting approximation M_{rc} is an optimal rank k approximation of M in a least square sense. More precisely, M_{rc} minimizes the Frobenius norm of $\|M - M_{rc}\|$ [29]. The validity of the SVD, as an optimal low-rank approximation of a matrix with respect to the Frobenius norm, is stated by the Eckart-Young-Mirsky theorem [36, 37, 38].

Figure 3.1 visualizes the impact of rank reduction: The outer grid shapes correspond to the size of matrices as defined for regular SVD in Equation 3.14, but the effective size of SVD is smaller. Here, n is smaller than m such that Σ contains n singular values. As a consequence, only the first n left-singular vectors of U contribute to the result because the remaining vectors are multiplied with zero values. If the rank r of M is smaller than n , even more left-singular as well as some right-singular vectors can be ignored. This result is known as thin SVD [41]. The truncated version SVD_k is represented by the dark colored cells.

In contrast to eigen decomposition, the singular value decomposition produces two orthogonal matrices. Therefore, SVD_K can reduce the size of components only if $k \ll \min(m, n)$. More precisely, k has to be selected such that

$$k(m + n + 1) < mn \quad (3.18)$$

Vice versa, a target rank that violates the constraint needs more than nm numbers such that decomposition has a worse compression ratio than saving the original matrix.

3.4. Implementation

As a widely used language in geo sciences and data sciences in general, we choose Python 3 to implement low-rank matrix approximation. Python provides a lot of useful libraries that integrate well in our given scenario. In the following, we present the main libraries and their features to implement and evaluate low-rank matrix approximation in a performant, reliable and structured way.

3.4.1. NetCDF File Format

NetCDF (Network Common Data Form) is a set of interfaces to store and access array-oriented data in a machine independent format [42]. It aims to simplify the exchange of scientific data and is widely used especially in geo sciences, e.g. EUMETSAT provides Level 1 and Level 2 data as NetCDF files [12]. The same applies to the MUSICA IASI algorithm which stores the retrieved atmospheric state in NetCDF datasets. Since the compression is applied to the output of the MUSICA IASI algorithm (see Section 2.2), we retain the data model for consistency and convenience and use NetCDF as well.

NetCDF is structured as follows: from a library point of view a NetCDF file is a dataset containing groups, variables, dimensions and attributes. Groups inside a dataset are referenced using paths in a similar way like directories in the Unix file system (e.g. /state/WV/avk). In this analogy, a dataset – or root group – corresponds to the root directory. A group may contain any number of variables, attributes and dimensions. Attributes are single valued and associated with a group or variable, for example to provide a description or unit to a variable, while variables are used to store array-oriented data. The dimensionality of variables is specified by the size of a given dimension. A variable can reference all dimensions in its group or parent groups. Therefore, multiple variables can share the same dimension, e.g. `atmospheric_grid_levels=29` is referenced by variables indicating the atmospheric state of different altitudes. The dimensionality of a variable is immutable after creation except for unlimited dimensions, e.g. `event` is an unlimited dimension. This allows to append other measurements along the event dimension afterwards [43].

Unfortunately, dimensionality of real world measurements is not consistent. Some measurements have a dynamic dimensionality, e.g. the number `atmospheric_grid_levels` varies up to 29 dependent on the topography. To address the problem, NetCDF maintains a mask for each value indicating its validity. In the case of `atmospheric_grid_levels`,

all referencing variables have a dimensionality of 29, but for deviating measurements non-existent levels are masked.

Masked arrays have two major drawbacks. First, the arithmetic is less performant compared to plain arrays since masked values have to be considered properly [44]. Second, NetCDF stores masked values with a default or user specified fill value. Normally, masked arrays have the same storage requirements as completely unmasked arrays. This is especially inefficient for the compression approach presented in Section 3.3: With an adaptive target rank with respect to the condition number and the threshold ϵ , the theoretical upper bound is the original rank. Especially the singular value decomposition would double the storage requirements if the decomposition of only one measurement has the original rank, because it produces two matrices instead of one. Even if the target rank is mostly significantly lower than the original rank, the target rank varies for different gases, variables and regions (see Figure 3.11b). Because storage efficiency depends only on the maximum rank within a NetCDF variable, a lower rank of other measurements rather introduces an unnecessary error than a better compression ratio.

We solve this problem by activating compression on decomposed variables. NetCDF compression is based on the zlib library and has been introduced in the forth major version [20]. Even if the compression ratio is expected to be limited for numerical data as described in related work, compression reduces the size of decomposed variables due to the significant amount of fill values (see Table 3.4).

3.4.2. Luigi Workflow Management

Luigi is a workflow management tool written in Python that aims for the effective build of job pipelines for batch processing [45]. With three essential methods, the Luigi task interface is the central component to build a pipeline: (1) `requires()` returns a list of tasks the current task depends on. (2) `output()` defines the targets of the task's execution result (e.g. a NetCDF file). (3) `run()` implements the task execution. Since the method is called after all required tasks finished execution, their outputs are accessible using the `input()` method [46].

A Luigi task can be parametrized with values of different types. They include common types like string, boolean, integer and float but also custom types like date range. Parameters are injected via the class constructor or the command line interface. Together with the class name, the set of parameters identifies a task uniquely. Internally, two tasks of the same class and an equally valued set of parameters are mapped to the same task instance within a worker. As a consequence, the same task is executed only once even if it is scheduled multiple times [47].

For this thesis, the following tasks are implemented for compression and evaluation of the atmospheric state:

- **MoveVariables:** Creates a copy of an input dataset and moves variables into groups. Since the decomposition of matrices increases the amount of variables, grouping ensures that variables are neatly arranged.
- **CompressDataset:** Compresses all suitable input variables using singular value decomposition (Section 3.3.3) respectively eigen decomposition (Section 3.3.2). The

decomposition method is determined by dimensionality and name of the variable. The degree of compression can be specified with respect to Equation 3.17 by the task parameter threshold.

- **CompressDateRange:** Extends the Luigi WrapperTask. This type of task does not produce any output but in this case schedules multiple CompressDataset subtasks of measurements within a parameterizable date interval [48].
- **DecompressDataset:** Takes a dataset decomposed by CompressDataset and reconstructs the original matrix structure. Since singular value decomposition and eigen decomposition are lossy, the reconstruction is an approximation of the original matrices.
- **SelectSingleVariable:** Creates a copy of a dataset containing only the one variable specified by task parameter `variable`. The task is needed to evaluate the compression ratio of a single variable because the NetCDF library does not provide information about the storage requirements of a variable.
- **EvaluationCompressionSize:** The task is parameterized with a list of gases, variables and thresholds. For each parameter combination, `SelectSingleVariable` is executed on the output of `CompressDataset`. Together with the original size of each variable (`SelectSingleVariable` performed on `MoveVariables`), the task reports the size of each variable depending on the threshold.
- **VariableErrorEstimation:** Calculates the error estimation of the given gas, variable and thresholds as defined in Section 3.5.1.
- **EvaluationErrorEstimation:** Collects the output of `VariableErrorEstimation` for all gases, variables and thresholds and generates a comma separated list with all error estimates.

The Luigi execution model follows the client server paradigm: A Luigi client running as a Python process submits a set of tasks to the central scheduler running as a web server. Per default, one client has one worker. If required, the number of workers can be increased to enable parallel task execution. In this case, the client creates one subprocess for each worker. If a worker is idle, it requests a new task from the central scheduler. Since the scheduler knows all submitted jobs and registered workers, it assigns a task only to one worker, thus each task is executed exactly once. As an alternative, tasks can be coordinated by a local scheduler in the client process. This is especially useful for testing and debugging purposes [49].

Implementing batch processing as a Luigi workflow has several advantages. Writing of a task's output can be easily implemented in an atomic way: Intermediate results are written to a temporary file and only if the task completes successfully (without any exception), the file is moved to the final destination specified by `output()` [48]. This prevents subsequent tasks from processing corrupted data.

Splitting long running jobs into smaller tasks with intermediate persistent results can significantly accelerate the execution time because tasks whose output already exist

are considered as completed. Whenever a process unintentionally quits (e.g. estimated processing time exceeded), all intermediate results are checkpoints where a new process can resume computation. Additionally, subtasks may increase the reusability of components; e.g. `DecompressDataset` can be used by users who would like to work with reconstructed data, but it is also required by `EvaluationErrorEstimation` to estimate the error introduced by matrix approximation.

Luigi's central scheduler monitors all scheduled tasks and provides a web-based dashboard. It summarizes the current state of tasks (pending, running, done, failed), shows parameters and execution times, but also displays custom status messages as well as the current progress in percentage for running tasks if implemented. Furthermore, all registered workers and their current tasks are listed. In case of complex pipelines, the dashboard can visualize the tasks as a dependency graph. Altogether, this information can be quite useful to track the processing of a pipeline.

Given the following example scenario that we compress the orbit files of one month using `CompressDateRange`. Within the range, there are 900 orbit files where each is processed by a worker. The job runs several hours and works well for most of the files except for two orbit files which contain corrupted data for unknown reasons. The monitor dashboard displays 898 done and two failed tasks. With the exception message and stacktrace, we are able to find and fix the root cause. As long as the patch does not affect the finished tasks, we can restart the same job. The workers will only process the two tasks with missing output. Due to atomic writes, failed tasks did not produce any valid output.

One major drawback of Luigi's central scheduler is its limited scalability. The documentation states: "[...] The assumption is that each task is a sizable chunk of work. While you can probably schedule a few thousand jobs, it's not meant to scale beyond tens of thousands[...]" [50]. Experiments have shown that 10,000 tasks submitted from 400 workers distributed over 20 compute nodes exceeded the capacity of a single-threaded scheduler [49]. In fact, the limit of reliable operation is probably even lower. As a workaround, each node used its own local scheduler with 20 local workers. This approach scales linear, but we can no longer track the tasks in the monitoring dashboard.

Another limitation of Luigi are missing logging capabilities at task level. If Python's logging module is used within a task, logs are written to the configured destination (standard out, standard err, file). In the case of executing multiple tasks in parallel on multiple workers, the logs are intermingled and debugging gets harder. To address this problem, we use Luigi's callback events to manage a custom log handler at task level [46, 51, 52]: The `START` event registers a handler that writes all incoming logs to a file with the same name as the output file but with `.log` extension. If `SUCCESS` is triggered, the task's execution time is logged and the log handler gets removed. The same happens for an incoming `FAILURE` event, but instead of execution time the exception message is logged.

As outlined above, skipping tasks with existent input has some great advantages for operational processing, but for testing purpose this might be inappropriate: We implemented several integration tests to assure integrity of all pipelines. If a change in the pipeline introduces a bug, the test would still pass as long as valid output from previous executions exists. We solve this problem by extending the task class with an optional parameter `force` that removes the task's output before execution. To enforce execution

Component	Specification	Task	Mean Runtime
CPU	Intel Xeon E5-2640 v2	CompressDataset	825.6 s
Frequency	2.00GHz	DecompressDataset	82.3 s
Cores	16		
Threads/Core	1		
Memory	128 GB		

Table 3.1.: Benchmark of mean task runtime on a compute node executing 16 tasks in parallel. Used samples are described in Table 3.2.

for an entire pipeline, the parameter `force_upstream` iterates recursively over all required tasks and removes their output if existent.

3.4.3. NumPy and SciPy

NumPy is the de facto standard library for multidimensional array data in Python. Also variables in NetCDF datasets are returned as a multidimensional masked NumPy array. SciPy focuses on linear algebra and numeric computations based on NumPy arrays. The features provided by both libraries are not completely distinct, but they are rather closely coupled, e.g. both libraries provide a method for singular value decomposition [53].

For eigen decomposition, we calculate eigenpairs with `numpy.linalg.eig()`. For performance reasons, the method’s implementation is based on the `_geev` routine provided by the Linear Algebra Packages (LAPACK) written in Fortran 90 [54, 55]. In theory, the eigenvalues of a real symmetric matrix are nonnegative real numbers [31], but in practice, noise matrices stored in NetCDF datasets are not exactly symmetric due to floating point precision. For some measurements these inaccuracies cause complex eigenpairs as a solution. To address this problem, we enforce symmetry of noise matrices by calculating the mean with their transpose $(N + N^T)/2$. Furthermore, floating point errors restrict noise matrices to be positive semi-definite. This results in some negative eigenvalues although they should be nonnegative. As defined in Equation 3.13, we consider only eigenpairs with positive eigenvalues.

For singular value decomposition we use `scipy.linalg.svd()` which is also based on a LAPACK routine called `svddd`. In contrast to `svdxx` (another Fortran routine for SVD), the implementation uses “a more efficient divide and conquer approach for computation” [56]. Since singular value decomposition is defined for arbitrary shaped matrices, we do not face the issues of complex or negative eigenvalues as described above.

Even if NumPy respectively SciPy allows multithreaded computation, we limit the number of threads to one per task. Instead, we create a worker for each available core. Table 3.1 summarizes the mean task execution time. Due to the simplicity of reconstruction by multiplication of components, the reconstruction of a dataset is much faster than the decomposition. The compression runtime is acceptable because it is usually performed only once per orbit and because it is negligible compared to the runtime of the computation-intensive MUSICA IASI algorithm.

```
from netCDF4 import Dataset
from iasi import Composition

# get required data
dataset = Dataset('/path/to/compressed/netcdf/file.nc')
number_of_levels = dataset['atm_nol'][...]
decomposed_group = dataset['state/WV/avk']

# use composition factory to reconstruct original data as masked array
composer = Composition.factory(decomposed_group)
wv_averaging_kernel = composer.reconstruct(number_of_levels)
```

Figure 3.2.: Minimal working example of the data reconstruction API

3.4.4. Data Reconstruction API

With `DecompressDataset`, we proposed a way to permanently reconstruct a compressed dataset. This approach is not optimal in terms of storage requirements and is only useful if files are temporarily compressed for transmission. As an alternative, we provide a Python module to access and reconstruct decomposed matrices as illustrated by Figure 3.2.

The factory method of the `Composition` class is able to determine the decomposition type by the group object. Together with the number of atmospheric levels, the matrices can be reconstructed in a transparent way, no matter which gas or variable it concerns. Since the data is only in memory, the reconstruction API allows to process and analyse atmospheric state in a storage-efficient way. Compared to the compression of matrices, the reconstruction is faster because it is only based on multiplication of components. However, reconstruction is slower than direct access of a NetCDF variable: Besides overhead introduced by multiplication of components, the I/O is also slower because the NetCDF compression is enabled (see Section 3.4.1).

3.5. Evaluation

Low-rank matrix approximation, as defined in Section 3.3, is parameterizable with a threshold value ϵ that controls the target rank of decomposition. ϵ affects both the loss in information as well as the compression factor. To find a good tradeoff between those opposing criteria, we need a meaningful metric that quantifies the loss in information.

3.5.1. Error Metrics

For numerical data, the mean squared error (MSE) is a popular general-purpose error measure. It is particularly suitable to quantify the overall similarity of data points. With application to averaging kernels and noise matrices, this is not an optimal measure since the importance of precision varies for different levels. Furthermore, the MSE does not indicate to which degree an error influences further applications of matrices such that the upper limit of an acceptable MSE is hard to estimate.

To address this problem, we define an alternative error metric that quantifies the variances introduced by compression. These variances are expressed by a covariance matrix S_{rc} , in the following denoted as reconstruction error. The reconstruction error is based on the error estimation of the averaging kernel of water vapour as used by Schneider et al. [18] and is adapted to other gases and temperature. In the following, we express the existing variances in matrices by a covariance matrix S denoted as original error.

3.5.1.1. A Priori Covariance

The averaging kernel indicates to which degree the retrieved gas concentrations are influenced by real gas concentrations at another level. In order to assess the effect of the averaging kernel, we need to assume typical covariances of the atmospheric state. This a priori covariance matrix characterizes the magnitude of variations with respect to the a priori at a given level and how they are correlated to variations at another level. To build this covariance matrix, we assume a normal distribution with a respective standard deviation at each level and a correlation length describing the correlation between different levels. Let n be the number of atmospheric levels and h_i the altitude in meters of level i . For $\forall i, j \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ the a priori covariance matrix S_a is defined as

$$S_{a,i,j} = \alpha_i \alpha_j e^{-\frac{(h_i - h_j)^2}{2\sigma_i \sigma_j}} \quad (3.19)$$

where σ_i is the assumed correlation length and α_i the standard deviation at level i . Together, they model the atmospheric variances. Since the concrete values of S_a vary between gases and variables, we define the a priori covariance matrix individually for each error metric.

Figure 3.3.: Sample of the a priori correlation length of atmospheric gases and temperature with the tropopause at ~ 9.5 km

The contribution of the assumed correlation length to S_a is the same for all gases as well as the atmospheric temperature. The correlation length specifies the vertical extend of the correlation in the atmosphere. Figure 3.3 depicts this effect: The tropopause is at

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(a) A priori standard deviation $\alpha_{N_2O} = \alpha_{CH_4}$ (b) Resulting a priori covariance matrix $S_{a, N_2O} = S_{a, CH_4}$

Figure 3.4.: Sample of a priori covariance of greenhouse gases with tropopause at ~ 9.5 km

about 9.5 km for the given measurement. Here, the assumed correlation length is three kilometers. Due to the assumed gaussian distribution, roughly 60% of the variance at 9.5 km is in line with variances at 6.5 km and 12.5 km respectively. The higher the level, the greater the correlation length because atmospheric mixing processes have a lower vertical extent in the troposphere than the stratosphere. The upper bound of correlation length is assumed to be constant with six kilometers above an altitude of 25 kilometers. Note that the levels at y axis have a different scale than kilometers because the vertical profile of the atmosphere has a higher resolution at lower levels. The details of interpolation between surface, tropopause and stratosphere are documented in the implementation¹.

The standard deviation as a second factor models the typical variance or noise at a given level. As a scaling factor of the gaussian function in Equation 3.19, α describes the assumed relative variances at the given levels. In contrast to the correlation length, the standard deviation is individual for each gas and temperature. In the following, we describe the ideas behind our assumptions about the standard deviation except for water vapour. The latter requires special treatment described in Section 3.5.1.5.

Figure 3.4a depicts the standard deviation of the greenhouse gases N_2O and CH_4 . The greenhouse gases are mainly concentrated in the troposphere, while concentrations in the stratosphere are significantly lower. Due to lower concentrations, ascending molecules have a stronger influence on the relative abundancy in the stratosphere. The relative variability is further compound by atomic decay through radiation at higher altitudes. This is why the standard deviation is constantly low in the troposphere and increases with the beginning of the stratosphere. Since the effect is valid for both N_2O and CH_4 , their assumed standard deviations and covariances are respectively the same. Together, the a priori covariance of greenhouse gases is defined as

¹<https://github.com/weberandreseu/iasi/blob/master/iasi/evaluation.py>

Figure 3.5.: Sample of a priori covariance of nitric acid with tropopause at ~ 9.5 km

$$S_{a,GHG} = \begin{pmatrix} S_{a,N_2O} & 0 \\ 0 & S_{a,CH_4} \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.20)$$

where the zero values indicate that the variations in N_2O are not correlated to the variations in CH_4 .

Nitric acid (HNO_3) is a gas that is primarily caused by anthropogenic emissions of nitric oxide (NO) and nitrous oxide (N_2O) [57]. With that, the a priori standard deviation of HNO_3 is at the highest level near surface due to significant differences, e.g. between industrial regions and the sea surface (see Figure 3.5a). In the upper troposphere, HNO_3 interacts with other gases and is influenced by physical processes [57]. With the beginning of the stratosphere, the variances decrease due to less interaction.

For atmospheric temperature, the assumed standard deviation between the a priori (EUMETSAT L2) and the real temperature is with two Kelvin most significant at the surface as depicted in Figure 3.6a. Here, EUMETSAT L2 temperatures are particularly uncertain due to surface emissivity errors. Above surface, the standard deviation decreases due to higher precision in EUMETSAT L2 temperature. Starting with the stratosphere, the ozone layer increasingly absorbs most of the sun's ultraviolet radiation which might also affect the EUMETSAT L2 temperature uncertainty such that we assume a standard deviation of 1.5 Kelvin in the stratosphere [58].

3.5.1.2. Averaging Kernel

With a gas and measurement specific a priori covariance S_a , we can quantify the error contribution of an averaging kernel A by a covariance matrix S as proposed by Schneider et al. [18].

$$S(A) = (A - \mathbb{I})S_a(A - \mathbb{I})^T \quad (3.21)$$

Figure 3.6.: Sample of a priori covariance of atmospheric temperature with tropopause at ~ 9.5 km

Note the similarity to the definition of the covariance matrix in Equation 3.7: Instead of subtracting column means μ , we calculate the difference between the kernel matrix and identity matrix \mathbb{I} . Recap, the identity matrix corresponds to an ideal averaging kernel because the retrieved concentration at a given level would not be influenced by the real state at other levels. This is why the original error is rather characterized by a deviation from a perfect kernel than from an expected column mean.

Based on the definition of the original error, we adapt Equation 3.21 to determine the reconstruction error. Let A_{rc} be the reconstruction of the truncated singular value decomposition of an averaging kernel matrix A with respect to Equation 3.16. The covariance matrix of the reconstruction error S_{rc} is defined as

$$S_{rc}(A) = (A - A_{rc})S_a(A - A_{rc})^T \quad (3.22)$$

Analogous to the original error, the difference between A_{rc} and A quantifies the deviation of given values from expected values. With the gas specific a priori covariance matrix S_a , the importance of the reconstruction error is weighted for different levels with knowledge about the characteristics of gases.

3.5.1.3. Cross Averaging Kernel with Atmospheric Temperature

For cross averaging kernels with atmospheric temperature, the estimation of the original- and reconstruction error is slightly different than of the averaging kernels but consistent for all gases. The cross averaging kernel models the influence of real atmospheric temperature on the retrieved gas concentration. In a perfect world, retrieved gas concentrations would not depend on atmospheric temperatures. This expected ideal condition would be modeled by a zero-valued cross averaging kernel. Consequently, the error, introduced by atmospheric temperature, is the cross averaging kernel itself. Following this, we define the original error of a cross averaging kernel A_{Tatm} by the covariance matrix S equal to

$$S(A_{Tatm}) = A_{Tatm} S_{a,Tatm} A_{Tatm}^T \quad (3.23)$$

The reconstruction error of a cross averaging kernel is again analogously defined to an averaging kernel in Equation 3.22: Let $A_{Tatm,rc}$ be the reconstruction of the truncated singular value decomposition of a cross averaging kernel matrix A_{Tatm} with respect to Equation 3.16. The reconstruction error of $A_{Tatm,rc}$ is characterized by the covariance matrix S_{rc} defined as

$$S_{rc}(X) = (A_{Tatm} - A_{Tatm,rc}) S_{a,Tatm} (A_{Tatm} - A_{Tatm,rc})^T \quad (3.24)$$

3.5.1.4. Noise Matrix

The noise matrix is per definition an error measure of the IASI instrument. As a covariance matrix, the original error S of a noise matrix N is the matrix itself

$$S(N) = N \quad (3.25)$$

Let N_{rc} be the reconstructed noise matrix from a truncated eigen decomposition with respect to Equation 3.11. The reconstruction error of N_{rc} is characterized by the error covariance matrix S_{rc} defined as the absolute value of

$$S_{rc}(N) = N - N_{rc} \quad (3.26)$$

3.5.1.5. Special Case Water Vapour

In contrast to other gases, the error contribution for water vapour requires special treatment. As described in Section 2.3, we are rather interested in the isotopologue ratio $\{H_2O, \delta D\}$ than in the molecule ration $\{H_2O, HDO\}$. We introduced the $\{H_2O, \delta D\}$ -proxy state by an orthogonal transformation through the matrix P . This representation has the advantage that H_2O and δD are less correlated. Therefore, we can define their a priori covariances independently:

$$S_{a,WV} = \begin{pmatrix} S_{a,H_2O} & 0 \\ 0 & S_{a,\delta D} \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.27)$$

The a priori covariance matrices of humidity S_{a,H_2O} and isotopologues ratio $S_{a,\delta D}$ are visualized in Figure 3.7. While the correlation length is the same as for other gases, the standard deviation varies for both. Due to the high correlation of H_2O and HDO , the curves of α_{H_2O} and $\alpha_{\delta D}$ have the same characteristics but the amplitude of $\alpha_{\delta D}$ has approximately 10% of α_{H_2O} because the ratio HDO/H_2O is relatively invariable. The highest relative variability of water vapour occurs in the middle and upper troposphere where variations are caused by atmospheric processes like condensation and vertical transport. At the beginning of the stratosphere, the standard deviation decreases because concentrations of water vapour are much lower and the vertical transport is less significant.

For the estimation of the original error as well as the reconstruction error of water vapour, the definitions in Equations 3.21 - 3.26 are also valid. However, the matrices have

(a) A priori standard deviation α_{H_2O} (blue) and $\alpha_{\delta D}$ (orange) (b) Resulting a priori covariance matrix of S_{a,H_2O} . $S_{a,\delta D}$ has the same structure, but with other scale due to smaller standard deviation.

Figure 3.7.: Sample of a priori covariance of water vapour with tropopause at ~ 9.5 km

to be transformed to the proxy state in order to apply the formulas. The type 1 product of the water vapour's averaging kernel A'_{WV} is defined in Equation 2.5 and replaces the plain kernel A in Equations 3.21 and 3.22 for error estimation. Analogously, noise matrices N in Equations 3.25 and 3.26 are substituted by their type 1 product defined as

$$N'_{WV} = PN_{WV}P^T \quad (3.28)$$

For cross dependence between water vapour and atmospheric temperature, the transformation of the cross averaging kernel $A_{Tatm,WV}$ is defined as

$$A'_{Tatm,WV} = PA_{Tatm,WV} \quad (3.29)$$

and substitutes the plain kernel A_{Tatm} in Equations 3.23 and 3.24.

With type 1 transformed matrices, we can estimate the error of $\{H_2O, \delta D\}$. As stated in Section 2.3.2, the type 1 product lacks of interpretability because the atmospheric state does not relate to same air masses. As a solution, we adapt the sensitivity of the humidity kernel to the poorer sensitivity of the isotopologues ratio kernel, such that the effort of a separate error estimation for the type 2 product is worthwhile. Again, the above definitions in Equations 3.21 - 3.26 are also valid for type 2 products, but the matrices have to be replaced by their respective a posteriori corrected versions. For the averaging kernel, the correction to A''_{WV} is defined in Equation 2.7. The type 2 product of the water vapour noise matrices N_{WV} is defined as

$$N''_{WV} = CN'_{WV}C^T \quad (3.30)$$

and the transform of the cross averaging kernels $A_{Tatm,WV}$ as

$$A''_{Tatm,WV} = CA'_{Tatm,WV} \quad (3.31)$$

Date	Satellite	# Orbits	# Measurements
2016-02-01	MetOp-A	15	275.394
	MetOp-B	14	295.363
2016-08-02	MetOp-A	14	329.518
	MetOp-B	14	324.314
Total	2	57	1.224.589

Table 3.2.: Samples used for the evaluation

3.5.2. Parameter Selection

After the definition of a meaningful error metric, we estimate the error introduced by low-rank matrix approximation and compare it to the compression factor. Since the target rank is adaptive with respect to the threshold parameter ϵ , we can select an appropriate value of ϵ as a good tradeoff between the loss in information and the compression factor.

For evaluation, we estimate the error of all measurements for two days. To include the seasonal variances in the atmosphere, we respectively choose one day in winter and one in summer in northern hemisphere as described in Table 3.2. For each gas, we calculate the original error and the respective reconstruction error in dependence of $\epsilon = \{1e^{-2}, 1e^{-3}, 1e^{-4}, 1e^{-5}\}$. Together with the resulting compression ratios, we can individually determine ϵ for each gas. For brevity, we only discuss the results for water vapour in the section. The results of other gases are attached in Appendix A.1.

Figure 3.8 and 3.9 respectively depict the type 1 and type 2 error of water vapour. The values originate from the diagonal elements at a given altitude of error covariance matrices, such that the figures plot the mean error variances. The mean original error is marked by the dashed horizontal lines, while the mean reconstruction error is visualized by error bars. Figure 3.10 analogously visualizes the compressed sizes with respect to ϵ , where dashed lines mark the original sizes of the variables in zlib compressed form.

As can be seen in Figure 3.8a, the mean original error variance is above $0.1 \log(ppmv)^2$ at an altitude of 4.2 km. Taking the square root, the standard deviation is above $0.3 \log(ppmv)$. In contrast, the corresponding reconstruction error variance for $\epsilon = 1e^{-3}$ averages to $10^{-8} \log(ppmv)^2$. Taking the square root, the additional error introduced by the approximation (expressed as standard deviation) is $10^{-4} = 0.001 \log(ppmv)$. Looking at the corresponding compression ratio in Figure 3.10 and Table 3.3, we observe that the mean size of the averaging kernel is reduced to 58% of the original size.

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Figure 3.8.: Mean type 1 error of water vapour

Figure 3.9.: Mean type 2 error of water vapour

Figure 3.10.: Mean size per orbit of water vapour variables

Gas	Variable	Threshold	Original size	Compressed size	Percentage
WV	avk	1e-3	230.40 MB	132.63 MB	58%
	n	1e-3	222.63 MB	64.68 MB	29%
	Tatmxavk	1e-2	112.69 MB	60.83 MB	54%
GHG	avk	1e-3	223.82 MB	123.21 MB	55%
	n	1e-3	221.30 MB	59.47 MB	27%
	Tatmxavk	1e-2	112.28 MB	53.20 MB	47%
HNO3	avk	1e-3	52.31 MB	18.88 MB	36%
	n	1e-4	53.07 MB	16.62 MB	31%
	Tatmxavk	1e-2	55.80 MB	25.57 MB	46%
Tatm	avk	1e-2	57.14 MB	40.83 MB	71%
	n	1e-4	56.59 MB	28.24 MB	50%

Table 3.3.: The mean variable size of an orbit depending on the selected threshold value ϵ . The original size is based on zlib compression, while the compressed size is based on both zlib and low-rank matrix approximation.

When comparing the compression ratios, Figure 3.10 reveals significant differences between the singular value decomposition and the eigen decomposition. Since the eigen decomposition results in one matrix and one vector, its compression ratio is better than for singular value decomposition. Even for a lower threshold (more eigenvalues and eigenvectors) $\epsilon = 1e^{-5}$, the reduction in size is about 50%. In contrast, a singular value decomposition with the same ϵ requires even more storage than the original kernels because two matrices are saved instead of one. Another observation is the seasonal variation in size of the dataset: This is mainly caused by the different number of measurements (see Table 3.2), but in the following section we show that the season influences the target rank such that the seasonal variation may also affect the compression ratio.

Most importantly, the overall reconstruction error is magnitudes lower than the original error for all given threshold values and altitudes. This is even true for kernels approximated by singular value decomposition, where a target rank significantly lower than the original matrix rank is needed to reduce the size of matrices. With respect to the given error and the importance of the product, we select ϵ such that the reconstruction error is at least two magnitudes lower than the original error – but for most variables more than three magnitudes lower. The results are summarized in Table 3.3.

Low-rank matrix approximation is only applied to a subset of variables in a NetCDF dataset. Table 3.4 shows the effective compression ratio for a complete dataset including non-compressed variables: Zlib compression itself reduces the size of the dataset by 20%. One reason for this relative significant reduction are fill values introduced by the diverging number of levels and masked retrievals. Together with the low-rank matrix approximation, the mean size of a dataset is reduced by 58%. Taking zlib compression as a baseline, the gain by low-rank matrix approximation nearly halves the effective storage requirements.

Compression	Total Size	Mean Orbit Size	Percentage
None	116.65 GB	2046 MB	100 %
Zlib	93.99 GB	1649 MB	80 %
Low-Rank + Zlib	48.86 GB	857 MB	42 %

Table 3.4.: Effective storage requirements of orbit samples in Table 3.2. Zlib and low-rank matrix approximation are only applied to averaging kernels, noise matrices and cross kernels with atmospheric temperature. Other variables like result and a priori profile are also included but not compressed.

3.5.3. Distribution of the Reconstruction Error

The discussion in Section 3.5.2 considers only the mean values of the reconstruction error. For worst a case error estimation and a general understanding, we analyse the overall error distribution in the following.

Figure 3.11a compares the seasonal reconstruction error distribution in a geographic context. Within a geographically narrow area, there are higher errors as well as lower errors but there is no direct relation to the different climate zones or seasons visible. In contrast, Figure 3.11b depicts the geographic distribution of the target rank: Here, a clear correlation between the different climate zones and the target rank is visible. While higher target ranks are concentrated north from the equator during summer in the northern hemisphere, they are more southerly concentrated during winter in the northern hemisphere. These results underline that the degree of information in kernel matrices varies. Since the tropospheric layer with high variability in humidity is broader in tropical regions, the condition number indicates that the structure of kernel matrices is more complex such that a higher target rank is needed for an appropriate approximation.

Even if the seasonal and latitudinal dependency of the reconstruction error is very small compared to the target rank, there is a slight correlation between both: Figure 3.12 plots the error distribution by the target rank. It shows that kernels with a lower target rank tend to have an increased reconstruction error. From a quantitative point of view, the highest errors are caused by really rare events. If we filter the reconstruction error to the highest values, we observe that error-prone measurements in this sample are concentrated in the antarctic regions. Taking 10^{-6} as the maximum reconstruction error, the standard deviation is with approximately $10^{-3} = 0.01 \log(ppmv)$ still significantly lower than the mean original error. Later we show that the increased error in the antarctic regions might be explainable by the low sensitivity of the retrieval.

More problematic is the increased correlation between the reconstruction error and the target rank for noise matrices as shown in Figure 3.13. Here, the reconstruction error is significantly higher for matrices with a lower target rank. Furthermore, the number of outliers is higher compared to the averaging kernel (compare Figure 3.12a and 3.13a). The higher values in the error distribution can be explained by the floating point errors in the noise matrices. The given matrices are not necessarily positive semi-definite such that eigen decomposition partly produces negative eigenvalues. Since we ignore eigenpairs

(b) Target rank k with respect to ϵ Figure 3.11.: Seasonal comparison of reconstruction error and target rank of water vapour's averaging kernel with threshold $\epsilon = 1e^{-3}$

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(a) Measurement count in 60 bins

(b) Distribution by target rank

Figure 3.12.: Distribution of reconstruction error S'_{rc} of water vapour's averaging kernel with threshold $\epsilon = 1e^{-3}$

(a) Measurement count in 60 bins

(b) Distribution by target rank

Figure 3.13.: Distribution of reconstruction error S'_{rc} of water vapour's noise matrix with threshold $\epsilon = 1e^{-3}$

with negative eigenvalues, those decompositions might have a higher error and a lower target rank.

The general distribution by target rank indicates that the structure of noise matrices is more difficult to approximate by a low number of eigenpairs. Here, the condition number might not be an optimal criteria to identify all important eigenpairs.

3.6. Application

In Section 3.5, we discussed the error introduced by low-rank matrix approximation on basis of a domain specific theoretical error estimation. Since approximated matrices are rather operands than concrete measurements, we evaluate the influence of the reconstruction error in real applications in the following.

(a) Error histogram of all retrievals

(b) Error histogram of retrievals with high sensitivity

Figure 3.14.: The difference $\tilde{x} - \tilde{x}_{rc}$ of δD with respect to the retrieval formula in Equation 3.32 introduced by approximation of the averaging kernel. The samples include processed measurements of 2016-01-01.

As an use case, we choose the a posteriori optimized retrieval of water vapour's δD , as denoted in Figure 2.3 as *a posteriori processing*: The process retrieves the profile \tilde{x} under an a posteriori modified constraint by calculating

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{x} &= x_a + R^{-1}A^T(AR^{-1}A^T + S_{\epsilon_x})^{-1}(\hat{x} - x_a) \\ S_{\epsilon_x} &= (\mathbb{I} - A)S_a - (A - \mathbb{I})S_a(A - \mathbb{I})^T \end{aligned} \quad (3.32)$$

as proposed by Rodgers et al. in Equation (18) [59]. Note that this formula includes the matrix inverse, an error-prone operation, such that even small differences may accumulate to a significant error. To measure the reconstruction error, we calculate the profile \tilde{x} with the original averaging kernel A and \tilde{x}_{rc} with the reconstructed averaging kernel A_{rc} .

Figure 3.14a plots the distribution of deviation in the retrievals. For the vast majority of retrievals the absolute difference of δD is below 5‰ – the typical value range of δD retrievals is within $[-450\text{‰}, -50\text{‰}]$. However, for some retrievals the deviation is more significant. If we filter retrievals with low sensitivity (these retrievals will not be used in research applications), we eliminate all significant deviation as depicted in Figure 3.14b.

For climatological analysis, as presented in the following chapter, only high quality retrievals (with high sensitivity) are of interest. Therefore, we assume that the error introduced by low-rank matrix approximation is negligible – especially since original retrievals are also affected by noise.

4. Spatio-Temporal Analysis

Remote sensing measurements by the IASI instruments provide global observations of the atmospheric state including concentrations of water vapour and its isotopologue ratios. Characteristic distributions of $\{H_2O, \delta D\}$ -pairs are correlated with different climatological processes as described in Chapter 2. Since given data does not provide labels about the underlying processes such as drying by mixing or condensation and rainout, clustering as an unsupervised method is a promising approach to extract patterns from given data.

The spatial and temporal context is particularly important for the analysis with application to climate data because atmospheric processes are varying with time and region. A subfield of data mining that focuses on such kind of analysis is spatio-temporal clustering that aims to group objects based on their spatial and temporal similarity [7].

In this chapter, we discuss applications and related work of spatio-temporal clustering and formulate the problem statement for the given scenario. With DBSCAN and HDBSCAN, we use two general-purpose density-based clustering algorithms in a spatio-temporal context. For a better assessment of the clustered results, we evaluate different cluster metrics and their validity for the given data.

4.1. Related Work

Kisilevich et al. review approaches of spatio-temporal clustering and categorize the different problem statements based on data characteristics [7]. Their categorization depends on three criteria: The first is the spatial location of clustered objects which may be fixed or dynamic. The second is the temporal extension which describes the time span of the data. They denote unique events as spatio-temporal (ST) events since there is only one single snapshot of the given object. If an object is mutable over time, but only the latest state is available, the authors refer to such events as updated snapshots. Depending on the spatial location, the problem statement is about clustering of geo-referenced variables (fixed location) or moving points (dynamic location). If the complete history of an object's state is available, clustering is applied to geo-referenced time series (fixed location) or trajectories (dynamic location). The third criterion is the spatial extension which describes the shape of an object that should be clustered. Besides points, also lines or areas may represent objects of interest.

Cuzzocrea et al. apply k-means clustering to atmospheric data to detect high and low emitting sectors of greenhouse gases [60]. They cluster emissions to identify low and high emitting clusters, calculate the cluster centroids for each year and country and use the aggregated data to compare trends in emissions of respective countries.

Assem et al. perform spatio-temporal clustering, based on data provided by the location-based social network Foursquare, to detect functional regions in Manhattan [61]. To

determine the varying functionalities of a city district over daytime, they categorize location check-ins (shopping, residence, etc.). For each label they count the check-ins within each district (by zip code). By clustering the aggregated data they obtain areas with similar functionalities. They evaluate their results using different clustering algorithms (hierarchical-, k-means- and spectral clustering) and time slots. To determine an appropriate number of clusters for each time slot, they use the Silhouette Index to select the best performing parameters.

Birant et al. introduce with ST-DBSCAN a clustering algorithm based on DBSCAN that is adapted to spatio-temporal data [62]. In contrast to DBSCAN (described in Section 4.2.1), ST-DBSCAN takes four parameters $\{\epsilon_1, \epsilon_2, m_{pts}, \Delta\epsilon\}$. While ϵ_1 is only applied to spatial features, ϵ_2 is a separate distance threshold for non-spatial features. As another extension, they address the problem of adjacent clusters. In some applications the clusters may be spatially adjacent such that a clustering algorithm could tend to merge those clusters, even if their objects are in total more distant in non-spatial features. To address this problem, the algorithm compares the object's non-spatial values with the average cluster values before each cluster assignment. If the difference is larger than $\Delta\epsilon$, the object is not assigned to the cluster. Therefore, the clustered results are forced to contain similar non-spatial values with respect to $\Delta\epsilon$. The third ST-DBSCAN extension is the density factor of a cluster which aims to improve the robustness against misclassification of noise points in applications with varying cluster densities.

4.2. Spatio-Temporal Clustering

The clustering of spatio-temporal data can be achieved by general-purpose clustering algorithms ([61, 60]) as well as by specialized variants ([62]). For pattern mining in the $\{H_2O, HDO\}$ -space, we choose the density-based general-purpose clustering algorithms DBSCAN and HDBSCAN.

4.2.1. DBSCAN

Density-based spatial clustering of applications with noise (DBSCAN) is a clustering algorithm presented by Ester et al. in 1996 [63]. DBSCAN is widely used in several domains but is also established as the theoretical basis of adapted clustering algorithms [62, 64]. The notion of density-based clustering is the assumption that objects belonging to the same group are concentrated in dense regions and are separated from objects of other groups by sparse regions [62]. A density-based clustering algorithm reveals such groups. To achieve this, the algorithm needs a measure for density.

DBSCAN estimates the density with respect to the parameters ϵ and m_{pts} (minimal points). ϵ is a spatial threshold: if the distance between two objects is less than or equal to ϵ , those objects are assumed to be close to each other. In contrast, m_{pts} is a quantitative threshold: if an object has at least m_{pts} close neighbors, it is assumed to reside in a dense region. For the measurement of distances between objects, an arbitrary distance metric can be used, for example euclidean- or manhattan-distance. The choice depends on the nature of the data and is independent of the DBSCAN concept [63].

To introduce a more formal vocabulary, we use the DBSCAN* definition of Campello et al. that is slightly adapted from the original DBSCAN definition but allows a better comparison with HDBSCAN [63, 64]: Let $X = \{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$ be a data set of n objects, and let D be an $n \times n$ matrix containing the pairwise distances $d(x_p, x_q)$, $x_p, x_q \in X$, for a metric distance $d(\cdot, \cdot)$. We define density-based clusters on core objects alone:

Definition 1 (Core object). An object x_p is called a core object with respect to ϵ and m_{pts} if its ϵ -neighborhood contains at least m_{pts} many objects, i.e., if $|N_\epsilon(x_p)| \geq m_{pts}$, where $N_\epsilon(x_p) = \{x \in X | d(x, x_p) \leq \epsilon\}$ and $|\cdot|$ denotes cardinality. An object is called noise if it is not a core object.

Definition 2 (ϵ -Reachable). Two core objects x_p and x_q are ϵ -reachable with respect to ϵ and m_{pts} if $x_p \in N_\epsilon(x_q)$ and $x_q \in N_\epsilon(x_p)$.

Definition 3 (Density-Connected): Two core objects x_p and x_q are density-connected with respect to ϵ and m_{pts} if they are directly or transitively ϵ -reachable.

Definition 4 (Cluster): A cluster C with respect to ϵ and m_{pts} is a non-empty maximal subset of X such that every pair of objects in C is density-connected.

Following the definitions of DBSCAN*, all objects within a cluster are core objects. Vice versa, non-core objects are noise. The original DBSCAN definition deals a bit different with noise: If a non-core object $x_p \in X$ has a core object $x_q \in X$ in the ϵ -neighborhood such that $d(x_p, x_q) \leq \epsilon$, x_p is denoted as a border object. The border object x_p is part of the same cluster as x_q instead of being considered as noise. Noise objects are neither border nor core-objects [63, 64].

4.2.2. HDBSCAN

Hierarchical DBSCAN (HDBSCAN) is a successor of DBSCAN presented by Campello et al. in 2013. In contrast to DBSCAN, it provides a hierarchy of clusters which are not based on a global density threshold. Therefore, HDBSCAN is able to extract clusters of different densities from a data set [64, 65].

HDBSCAN takes two input parameters: m_{pts} (minimal points) and m_{clSize} (minimal cluster size). Those thresholds are used in different parts of the algorithm but both are a measure for the density such that $m_{pts} = m_{clSize}$ is a reasonable choice. Based on the terminology and notation of DBSCAN*, we define the building components of HDBSCAN as described in [64]:

Definition 5 (Core Distance): The core distance of an object $x_p \in X$ with respect to m_{pts} , $d_{core}(x_p)$, is the distance from x_p to its m_{pts} -nearest neighbor (incl. x_p)

Definition 6 (ϵ -Core Object): An object $x_p \in X$ is called an ϵ -core object for every value of ϵ that is greater than or equal to the core distance of x_p with respect to m_{pts} , i.e., if $d_{core}(x_p) \leq \epsilon$.

Figure 4.1.: HDBSCAN cluster extraction based on the mutual reachability graph $G_{m_{pts}}$ [66]

Definition 7 (Mutual Reachability Distance): The mutual reachability distance between two objects x_p and x_q in X with respect to m_{pts} is defined as $d_{mreach}(x_p, x_q) = \max\{d_{core}(x_p), d_{core}(x_q), d(x_p, x_q)\}$.

Definition 8 (Mutual Reachability Graph): It is a complete graph, $G_{m_{pts}}$, in which the objects of X are vertices and the weight of each edge is the mutual reachability distance (with respect to m_{pts}) between the respective pair of objects.

The mutual reachability graph can be seen as cheap distance measure between objects that respects their density: By computing pairwise distances between all objects, an object's core distance can be directly read from the resulting distance matrix. The core distance of an object is a measure of its density: Objects with lower core distances are part of denser regions than objects with higher core distances with respect to m_{pts} . By taking the maximum of original- and object's core-distances, the mutual reachability distance between close (with respect to $d(\cdot, \cdot)$) objects is increased, if one object resides in a sparse region. Otherwise the mutual reachability distance is the original distance [66].

The resulting mutual reachability graph is closely related to the DBSCAN* definition above [64]: Let $G_{m_{pts}, \epsilon} \subseteq G_{m_{pts}}$ be the graph obtained by removing all edges from $G_{m_{pts}}$ having weights greater than ϵ . From Definitions 4, 6, and 8, it is straightforward to infer

that clusters according to DBSCAN* w.r.t. m_{pts} and ϵ are the connected components of ϵ -core objects in $G_{m_{pts}, \epsilon}$; the remaining objects are noise. Consequently, all DBSCAN* partitions for $\epsilon \in [0, \infty)$ can be produced in a nested, hierarchical way by removing edges in decreasing order of weight from $G_{m_{pts}}$.

Instead of removing all edges in decreasing order, the HDBSCAN algorithm extracts the minimum spanning tree (MST) of $G_{m_{pts}}$ and adds reflexive edges to each object weighted with its core distance (see Figure 4.1a). The MST has the property that each removal of an edge splits a previously connected graph into two isolated subgraphs. Those subgraphs connect objects of the same cluster. The hierarchy of clusters can be visualized by a dendrogram as shown in Figure 4.1b [66].

Common applications require for each object one concrete label rather than multiple possible labels such that the cluster hierarchy needs to be flattened. The output of DBSCAN* corresponds to a horizontal cut in the dendrogram at the height of the global parameter ϵ . HDBSCAN takes another approach by cutting the hierarchical tree at different levels. To achieve this, the cluster hierarchy is first simplified to a condensed tree that contains only significant component splits. The condensed tree is constructed by iterating top-to-bottom through the dendrogram. For each split, the number of objects in both subcomponents is considered:

- i If both subcomponents are greater than or equal to m_{clSize} , the split is significant and remains in the condensed tree. Both subcomponents get a new label.
- ii If both subcomponents are smaller than m_{clSize} , the parental component disappears (the objects in the component are marked as noise).
- iii If one subcomponent is smaller than m_{clSize} , the smaller subcomponent disappears and the greater subcomponent keeps the label of the parental component.

The resulting condensed tree is visualized in Figure 4.1c. The vertically shrinking components visualize the loss of objects [64, 66].

Normally, the condensed tree significantly reduces the number of clusters, but they are still in a hierarchy such that the question of the best cluster subset remains. HDBSCAN answers this with the cluster stability measure: intuitively, if a cluster remains unchanged (not splitting into smaller clusters and slowly losing objects) for a wide range of density thresholds – or ϵ -distances in case of DBSCAN* – it is assumed to be stable. More formally, for the density measure $\lambda = 1/distance$ the stability of a cluster C_i is defined as

$$stability(C_i) = \sum_{x \in C_i} (\lambda_x - \lambda_{clSplit}) \quad (4.1)$$

where $\lambda_{clSplit}$ and λ_x are the respective lambda values when cluster C_i occurs (case i above) and object x falls out of C_i (case ii & iii above). Visually, the stability of a cluster corresponds to the area of a cluster in the condensed tree as depicted in Figure 4.1c. The best subset of clusters maximizes the overall stability. In the given example, this subset is highlighted in Figure 4.1d [64, 66].

4.3. Method

Following the criteria discussed by Kisilevich et al. [7], the given atmospheric data allows two approaches of clustering: The first approach considers air masses as objects of interest which are moving with time and have a variable humidity and isotopologues ratio. The IASI instrument provides updated snapshots twice a day but there is no mapping to previous snapshots of the same air mass such that the given data allows only clustering of moving points rather than of trajectories. The other approach is to choose fixed regions as objects of interest and to cluster over $\{H_2O, \delta D\}$ data points as time series of geo-referenced variables.

4.3.1. Data Selection

We evaluate spatio-temporal clustering based on the IASI measurements of the MetOp-A and -B satellites. Since the elapsed time between the overpasses of both satellites is roughly one hour, measurements can be grouped into a morning and an evening overpass. Instead of clustering time series of $\{H_2O, \delta D\}$ -pairs, we use the temporal segregation caused by the measurement process: the algorithm respectively clusters all measurements of the morning or evening overpass based on the features $\{lat, lon, H_2O, \delta D\}$. With the exclusion of the temporal dimension through grouping measurements by daytime, the datasets are more compact while temporal similarity within clusters is still given. Following the criteria by Kisilevich et al. [7], our problem statement is the clustering of ST events.

For analysis, we work with the data produced by the a posteriori modification as briefly described in Section 3.6. The comparison between DBSCAN and HDBSCAN is based on the retrievals of evening overpasses in August 2016. We limit the geographic extent to an area from 50° N to 25° S and 45° W to 60° E and filter low quality measurements. The remaining number of samples averages to 20,200 measurements per evening. Because most interesting processes related to water vapour happen in the troposphere, we choose $\{H_2O, \delta D\}$ -pairs representing the atmospheric state at an altitude of 4.2 km above the sea surface.

4.3.2. Preprocessing

We choose the euclidean distance as a distance metric for clustering. Since the value ranges of $\{lat, lon, H_2O, \delta D\}$ are different, we have to scale the dimensions in a way that similar measurements are also numerically close. One way to achieve this is to normalize the values by subtracting the mean μ and to scale to the standard deviation σ : $x' = (x - \mu)/\sigma$ [67]. However, this approach is inappropriate for the given data: if the geographic area is big enough, two measurements may be considered as numerically close compared to the $\{H_2O, \delta D\}$ -space, even if they are geographically several hundreds of kilometers apart. To address this problem, we implement a custom transformation that normalizes the values with respect to the scaling parameters $\{km, hum, iso\}$:

$$lat' = \frac{lat \cdot 111^{km/^\circ}}{km}, \quad lon' = \frac{lon \cdot \cos(lat) 111^{km/^\circ}}{km}, \quad H_2O' = \frac{\log(H_2O)}{hum}, \quad \delta D' = \frac{\delta D}{iso} \quad (4.2)$$

Before normalization, the transformation converts the unit of the coordinates from degrees into kilometers. There are 360 latitudinal degrees around the globe which correspond to the distance given by the earth's circumference of 40,000 km, i.e. the transform from degrees into kilometers is $\frac{40,000\text{km}}{360^\circ} \approx 111\text{km}/^\circ$. The distance between two longitudes is maximal at the equator and shrinks towards the poles such that the longitude distance depends on the cosine of the corresponding latitude.

The calculated euclidean distance between two transformed coordinates deviates from the real geographic distance. The spherical distortion increases with the distance of coordinates. Since the clustering algorithms should group only nearby measurements (neighborhood with some predefined kilometers distance), the deviation is expected to be negligible. As an advantage, the feature transformation is straightforward and the spatial dimension does not require a special treatment such that any general-purpose clustering algorithm or distance metric can be applied.

One limitation of the described transformation is the lack of modeling spatial similarity at the antimeridian: Measurements near 180° W are numerically faraway from 180° E, even if they are geographically side by side. Since the selected data is within 90° W and 90° E, this limitation does not affect the analysis, but has to be addressed for analysis of geographical larger areas.

4.3.3. Cluster Validation

Due to the missing ground truth in unsupervised learning, the validity of clusters is a main issue in cluster analysis. Plots may provide an intuition of the cluster quality for small low-dimensional datasets, but with increasing samples and dimensions the visualization becomes more difficult. Furthermore, visual interpretation tends to be subjective and lacks of comparability, hence a more objective quality measure would be desirable for a quantitative validation of large datasets.

In the last decades, several cluster validation techniques have been proposed to address this problem. The notion of all approaches is to provide a measure for the separation of clusters. In the following, we introduce three cluster validation indexes chronologically sorted and with increasing complexity.

4.3.3.1. Davies–Bouldin Index

The Davies–Bouldin Index is a fairly simple validation measure proposed by Davies and Bouldin [68]. For a set of clusters $U = C_1, \dots, C_l$ the index is defined as

$$DB(U) = \frac{1}{l} \sum_{i=1}^l \max_{i \neq j} \left\{ \frac{\Delta C_i + \Delta C_j}{\delta(C_i, C_j)} \right\} \quad (4.3)$$

where $\delta(C_i, C_j)$ is an inter-cluster distance measure between C_i and C_j and $\Delta(C_i)$ is an intra-cluster distance measure [69]. For both distance measures, there are several metrics as presented by Bolshakova et al. [69], e.g single- or average-linkage and complete- or average-diameter. We choose for $\Delta(C_i)$ the average distance of all objects in C_i to centroids

of C_i (centroid diameter), and for $\delta(C_i, C_j)$ the distance between centroids of C_i and C_j as implemented in the SciKit-Learn library [70].

A low DB score indicates a good clustering result with zero as the lowest possible value. For the selected distance measures, the score of a single cluster decreases below one if the centroid of the next cluster is more distant than the sum of both centroid diameters [69, 68].

4.3.3.2. Silhouette Index

The Silhouette Index is a cluster validation measure proposed by Rousseeuw [71]. At a first stage, the index defines a quality measure for each object, called silhouette width: Let x be an object of the cluster C_i . The silhouette width of x is defined as

$$s(x) = \frac{b(x) - a(x)}{\max\{a(x), b(x)\}} \quad (4.4)$$

where $a(x)$ is the average distance between x and all other objects $x_p \in C_i$ and $b(x)$ is the minimal average distance from x to all $x_p \in C_j, j \neq i$. The silhouette width is a relative confidence measure for an object's cluster assignment within the interval $[-1, 1]$. If $s(x)$ is positive, the other objects in the same cluster are on average closer than the objects in the next cluster. Vice versa, a negative silhouette width indicates that other objects in the assigned cluster are on average farther away than objects in the next cluster [71, 69, 61].

At the next stage, the silhouette value of a cluster C_i is the mean silhouette width $s(x)$ for all $x \in C_i$. The overall silhouette score for a set of clusters is their average silhouette value [69].

4.3.3.3. Density-Based Cluster Validation

Density-Based Cluster Validation (DBCV) is a cluster validity index proposed by Moulavi et al [10]. In contrast to the validation indexes above, DBCV does not minimize the variances of objects within a cluster. Instead, DBCV is a relative measure that compares the intra-cluster density with the sparsity of regions between clusters. With that, DBCV promises to be more compliant with the notion of density-based clustering algorithms than the above validation scores.

To detect dense and sparse regions, the DBCV index takes a similar approach like HDBSCAN: The scoring algorithm also constructs a mutual reachability graph as shown in Definition 8 but with another distance measure than the core distance called all-points-core-distance ($a_{ptscoredist}$). Similar to Definition 5 of the core-distance, $a_{ptscoredist}$ is a measure of an object's sparsity. Instead of depending on a global density threshold m_{pts} , the $a_{ptscoredist}$ of an object $x \in C_i$ is the distance to the k -nearest object in C_i , where k depends on the cluster size $n = |C_i|$ and $k \approx n/\ln(n)$ [10].

Based on the adapted mutual reachability graph, the DBCV algorithm constructs a minimum spanning tree MST for each cluster C_i in a set of l clusters and estimates their densities as defined by Moulavi et al. [10]: *Let the set of internal edges in the MST be all edges except those with one ending vertex of degree one. Let the set of internal objects (vertices) be all objects except those with degree one. The density sparseness and separation of clusters are given by Definition 9 and 10:*

Definition 9 (*Density Sparseness of a Cluster*): The *Density Sparseness of a Cluster (DSC)* C_i is defined as the maximum edge weight of the internal edges in MST_{MRD} of the cluster C_i , where MST_{MRD} is minimum spanning tree constructed using $a_{pts}coredist$ considering the objects in C_i .

Definition 10 (*Density Separation*): The *Density Separation of a Pair of Clusters (DSPC)* C_i and C_j , $1 \leq i, j \leq l$ and $i \neq j$, is defined as the minimal reachability distance between the internal nodes of their MST_{MRD} s of clusters C_i and C_j .

Definition 11 (*Validity Index of a Cluster*): Using DSC and DSPC, the *Validity Index of a Cluster* C_i , $1 \leq i \leq l$ is defined as

$$V_C(C_i) = \frac{\min_{1 \leq j \leq l, j \neq i} \{DSPC(C_i, C_j)\} - DSC(C_i)}{\max \left\{ \min_{1 \leq j \leq l, j \neq i} \{DSPC(C_i, C_j)\}, DSC(C_i) \right\}}$$

The validity index of a cluster is the relative difference of its Density Sparseness and its minimal Density Separation. If the region between the nearest other cluster (w.r.t. DSPC) is denser than the sparsest area within the cluster itself (w.r.t. DSC), V_C tends to be negative. Vice versa, a positive V_C indicates that the overall density within a cluster is higher than the density in the surrounding region. The value range of V_C is the interval $[-1, +1]$. The total DBCV score for a set of clusters is their average V_C weighted by the cluster size [10].

For evaluation purpose we used the Python implementation of DBCV by Jenness [72], but unfortunately the library is not able to calculate the score for our datasets containing more than 20,000 samples within an acceptable period of time. We also evaluated another density-based cluster validation index – Cluster Density between and within cluster (CDBw) – by Halkidi et al. [73] with the same dataset, but the CDBw implementation by Lashkov [74] was also incapable to compute the scores for the given samples within an acceptable period of time.

As a more performant alternative, we use an approximation of DBCV provided by a Python implementation of HDBSCAN. The algorithm differs from the original definition in the construction of the MST: instead of using the all-points-core-distances $a_{pts}coredist$, the HDBSCAN implementation uses the mutual-reachability MST as introduced in Definition 8. Based on the tree, HDBSCAN can calculate the DBCV index on the fly since the underlying data structure is already available. Nevertheless, the authors warn that the approximated score might not be an objective measure of clustering performance but may be used to compare different model parameters [75].

4.3.3.4. Aggregation and General Statistics

Measurements are clustered and validated per day, thus we need to aggregate the results for a long-term analysis. Since each of the above indexes is defined per cluster and calculates the mean of all clusters, we average the daily scores weighted by the number of clusters. Additionally, we collect some general statistics about the clustering results for a better interpretability. These include the mean number of noise objects, the mean number of clusters and the mean cluster size weighted by the number of clusters.

4.4. Evaluation

For the comparison of DBSCAN and HDBSCAN, we need to find appropriate model parameters for both algorithms. We approach this by identifying parameters that produce visually promising results for one single day. Based on those parameters, we extend the parameter set to similar parameters until the visual results are less promising. Moreover, we extend the time frame to one month consisting of over 600,000 observations. For DBSCAN, we choose the parameter set $\epsilon = \{1.8, 2.0, 2.2, 2.4\}$ as neighborhood distances and $m_{pts} = \{8, 10, 12, 14\}$ as minimum number of objects in the ϵ -neighborhood. For HDBSCAN, we select $m_{pts} = m_{clSize} = \{10, 12, 14\}$ as possible thresholds for the estimation of core distances and minimal number of clusters.

Since the given features $\{lat, lon, H_2O, \delta D\}$ might have different contributions to the underlying atmospheric process, we also instantiate the transformation with different parameters. Those include $km = \{50, 60, 70, 80\}$ for the spatial dimension, $hum = \{0.11, 0.12, 0.13, 0.14\}$ for the humidity and $iso = \{6, 7, 8, 10\}$ for the isotopologues ratio. Altogether, we cluster over half a million measurements with 4^5 parameter combinations using DBSCAN and $3 \cdot 4^3$ parameter combinations using HDBSCAN.

4.4.1. Hyperparameter Analysis

Table 4.1 summarizes the top five results of each presented cluster validation index. Note that the DBCV score of DBSCAN is missing because the referenced implementation is unable to process the data volume within an acceptable period of time.

Starting with DBSCAN, the best five results respectively share with $km = 50$, $\epsilon = 1.8$ the lowest possible values and with $m_{pts} = 14$ the highest possible value. Considering the noise ratio of approximately 50%, the relation between the parameters turns out clearly: m_{pts} and ϵ are selected to maximize the number of noise. Together with a low valued spatial denominator km in the transformation (see Equation 4.2), the distance between clusters is maximized such that the Davies–Bouldin Index and the Silhouette Index perform better. Scaling parameters hum and iso affect the scores less due to the dominance of the spatial dimension.

In contrast, the relations between the HDBSCAN parameters are less clear. Again, all scores have a preference for the highest possible value for m_{pts} . As the main model parameter of HDBSCAN, $m_{mts} = m_{clSize}$ also affects the amount of noise, e.g. the parameter set of the best DBCV result has on average 3,930 noise objects instead of 4,196 only by replacing $m_{mts} = 14$ with $m_{mts} = 10$ (not included in table). The DBCV score for this result drops with 0.183 from rank 1 to 139 of 192. In contrast, the Davies–Bouldin Index has also a preference for a high m_{pts} value, but results with a low spatial and high isotopic scalar in more clusters and less noise. A varying spatial denominator indicates less dependence on the spatial dimension than the DBSCAN scores.

For both shared scores, HDBSCAN outperforms DBSCAN with equal or better results and roughly 20% noise instead of 50%. For top results, DBSCAN tends to extract many small clusters due to a small ϵ -neighborhood. In contrast, HDBSCAN reveals fewer but bigger clusters since the density threshold is adapted to the density of a region with respect to the cluster stability rather than defined globally with a static ϵ . Furthermore, the results

show that different scores do not have a clear consensus about optimal parameters: Out of 1,216 clustering results, there is not one duplicated parameter set within the top 25 entries in Table 4.1.

4.4.2. Visual Validation

For visual validation, we plot the clustered results of both algorithms. The HDBSCAN plots are based on the best DBCV score. Because the top scores of DBSCAN contain too much noise, we choose for the DBSCAN plots a visually more promising parameter set $\{\epsilon = 2.2, m_{pts} = 12\}$. To achieve a two dimensional visualization, we separate the spatial domain from the $\{H_2O, \delta D\}$ -space. Since the $\{H_2O, \delta D\}$ -space contains many overlapping clusters, we have to reduce the geographic extent to a smaller area.

In the domain of water isotopologues, there is no clear definition of a good cluster partition. Nevertheless, the clusters should fulfil some basic criteria as outlined by Noone et al. [8]: first, a cluster should reveal a linear relationship between H_2O and δD . This means that the cluster shape should tend to be more tubular than globular in the $\{H_2O, \delta D\}$ -space. Second, the geographic extent of a cluster should be limited because atmospheric processes are location specific. The criteria are purposely vague formulated because the pattern discovery is part of the research question.

Figure 4.2 visualizes the clustered results of the DBSCAN algorithm. As a density-based algorithm, DBSCAN can reveal arbitrary shaped clusters, e.g. in the spatial domain, clusters are often non-convex and more tubular than globular. A limitation of DBSCAN is shown by the north western green cluster in Figure 4.2a: The algorithm merges many measurements, although they are separated by a less dense region, because the measurements are dense enough to be classified as core objects with respect to ϵ . Those measurements link both clusters such that the extent of resulting clusters is too wide to be matched to a single atmospheric process.

Even if the clusters mainly follow the spatial structure, the $\{H_2O, \delta D\}$ -space also contributes to the separation of clusters: Comparing Figure 4.2b and 4.2c, the light yellow cluster is overlapped with the cyan cluster in the spatial domain but separated in the $\{H_2O, \delta D\}$ -space. The same applies to the green and the dark blue clusters, where some of the measurements are geographically close, but separated in the $\{H_2O, \delta D\}$ -space.

Figure 4.3 shows the clustered results of HDBSCAN for the same data. In contrast to DBSCAN, many of the previously huge clusters are divided into smaller clusters including the north-western cluster. This can be explained by the hierarchical structure of HDBSCAN that allows to produce clusters of different densities. Due to the optimization of the cluster stability, splitting into smaller clusters produces more reliable results than a single cluster (with respect to the varying density measures λ).

In a direct comparison, HDBSCAN does not strictly tend to split clusters. For example in the region around Cairo (30°N 30°E, Figures 4.2a and 4.3a) DBSCAN separates the observations while HDBSCAN summarizes them into one bigger cluster (light green). However, the resulting cluster still has an acceptable geographic extent compared to the largest cluster in Figure 4.2a. The same also happens in the $\{H_2O, \delta D\}$ -space. Here, the differences are less significant but for instance the previously overlapped clusters (see

km	hum	iso	m_{pts}	ϵ	db	sil	n_noise	n_cl	cl_size
50	0.14	7	14	1.8	0.642	0.234	9049.19	124.77	89.36
50	0.13	7	14	1.8	0.643	0.237	9222.81	124.65	88.06
50	0.13	8	14	1.8	0.645	0.227	8430.58	126.71	92.88
50	0.12	7	14	1.8	0.645	0.241	9443.35	123.35	87.20
50	0.13	6	14	1.8	0.645	0.260	10243.23	120.55	82.59
50	0.11	6	14	1.8	0.649	0.261	10718.52	117.77	80.50
50	0.13	6	14	1.8	0.645	0.260	10243.23	120.55	82.59
50	0.12	6	14	1.8	0.649	0.254	10454.97	119.13	81.80
50	0.14	6	14	1.8	0.648	0.253	10063.97	120.94	83.81
50	0.11	7	14	1.8	0.648	0.243	9698.61	122.65	85.62

(a) Scores by DBSCAN

km	hum	iso	m_{pts}	dbcv	db	sil	n_noise	n_cl	cl_size
80	0.12	7	14	0.237	0.672	0.234	4195.84	81.48	196.40
70	0.11	6	14	0.229	0.669	0.232	4050.10	80.52	200.57
80	0.14	7	14	0.221	0.663	0.232	4040.58	80.94	199.65
70	0.12	6	14	0.219	0.666	0.255	4268.97	83.23	191.41
80	0.13	6	14	0.219	0.679	0.223	3904.42	77.06	211.45
50	0.13	10	14	0.209	0.633	0.225	3587.81	85.87	193.45
50	0.12	10	14	0.192	0.634	0.233	3712.23	87.23	189.02
50	0.14	10	14	0.194	0.637	0.230	3569.23	86.03	193.30
50	0.11	10	14	0.186	0.640	0.224	3547.42	84.77	196.43
50	0.13	10	12	0.188	0.641	0.222	3605.97	99.90	166.09
70	0.13	10	14	0.170	0.650	0.261	4086.32	86.61	186.04
70	0.12	10	14	0.174	0.649	0.260	4023.58	85.32	189.58
70	0.14	10	14	0.187	0.647	0.258	4043.39	86.74	186.25
70	0.12	6	14	0.219	0.666	0.255	4268.97	83.23	191.41
80	0.12	10	14	0.200	0.653	0.252	4040.35	84.19	191.93

(b) Scores by HDBSCAN

Table 4.1.: Top 5 scores of the respective clustering algorithms based on evening overpasses in August 2016. The mean number of measurements is 20,200 per evening. Bold scores mark the best result for a given metric. Legend: *km*, *hum*, *iso*: scaling factors of distance, humidity and isotopologues; *dbcv*: Density-Based Cluster Validation Index; *db*: Davies-Bouldin Index; *sil*: Silhouette Index; *n_noise*, *n_cl*: mean number of noise/cluster; *cl_size*: mean cluster size

Figure 4.2.: DBSCAN clustering results with the model parameter $\{\epsilon = 2.2, m_{pts} = 12\}$ and scaled with $\{km = 80, hum = 0.12, iso = 7\}$. Data is based on evening over-passes of 2016-08-01. Noise points are colored in light gray. Davies–Bouldin Index = 0.769, Silhouette Index = 0.

(a) Wider continental region

(b) Smaller subregion as marked left

(c) Isotopologues clusters with centroids in marked subregion

Figure 4.3.: HDBSCAN clustering results with model parameter $m_{pts} = 14$ and scaled with $\{km = 80, hum = 0.12, iso = 7\}$. Data is based on evening overpasses of 2016-08-01. Noise points are colored in light gray.

Figures 4.2b and 4.2c) are now summarized by a bigger cluster (see Figures 4.3b at 10° S 35° E and Figure 4.3c dark green).

4.4.3. Summary

Altogether, we observe that the clustered results are heavily influenced by spatial features. This is primarily caused by filtering the retrievals: Clouds and other quality criteria introduce a spatial separation that mostly dominates over the $\{H_2O, \delta D\}$ -space. The quantitative and objective assessment of clustered results without knowledge about the underlying process remains as a major challenge in the cluster analysis. We conclude, that the Davies–Bouldin Index and the Silhouette Index are not suitable for DBSCAN hyperparameter optimization of the given data since they ignore noise as a quality criterion. But also for HDBSCAN we assess their validity as limited since they are better suited for convex clusters [70, 10]. Even if DBCV is only used as an approximated variant, we think that it is a more meaningful measure because it shares the notion of density-based clustering.

In direct comparison, we clearly prefer HDBSCAN over DBSCAN due to its robustness and simplicity. Instead of two parameters, a single parameter is already sufficient to achieve better results. While DBSCAN is highly sensitive to the global distance threshold ϵ , HDBSCAN estimates an appropriate density threshold on its own with respect to the cluster stability. With the capability to cluster groups of different densities, HDBSCAN integrates better in the nature of the given data.

5. Conclusion

5.1. Compression

With low-rank matrix approximation, we evaluated a general-purpose compression method for symmetric matrices as well as for arbitrary shaped matrices. The approach reduces the size of a dataset with various matrices by nearly 50%. Part of the compression gain is the adaptive target rank that exploits the varying degree of information using the condition number. In combination with zlib compression, the average file has 42% of the original size although the compression is only based on the intra coherence of measurements.

As a main contribution of this thesis, we introduced a meaningful domain specific error measure that compares the existing error in remote sensing data product with the additional error introduced by the matrix approximation with respect to atmospheric properties. Based on the error estimation, we identify appropriate compression parameters for each gas as a good tradeoff between the compression ratio and the loss in information. Our studies show that the practical impact for our application is negligible if the approximation error is magnitudes lower than the original error. Even if the error measure is application specific, our framework could be adapted to other domains where data is error-prone (e.g. measurements, simulations). The effort might be worthwhile especially if an error estimation is needed (for example for quality assurance).

Our evaluation reveals that the condition number might not be an optimal heuristic to minimize the approximation error. Especially rare measurements with low sensitivity and target rank tend to have an increased error. To address this issue, a lower bound for the target rank could reduce this effect. An alternative heuristic, for example “*retain 95% of the eigenvalues’ sum*”, might further reduce the error. Another issue is the susceptibility of the eigen decomposition towards rounding errors in a given matrix.

A solution that resolves current limitations would be the low-rank matrix approximation of multiple measurements grouped in one matrix as proposed by Velagar et al. [27]. With that, the eigen decomposition of noise matrices could be replaced by the more robust singular value decomposition and the randomized SVD variant by Halko et al. [28] is able to decompose even huge matrices [35]. By exploiting inter coherence of measurements, this approach promises an even better compression ratio. Nevertheless, this approach introduces new problems that need to be resolved. First, measurements have, with different number of levels, a variable dimensionality. One solution might be the filling of lower dimensioned vertical profiles with zero values, but this introduces a bias since a filled vector does not represent the real profile. Second, measurements might interact with each other; e.g. the structure of kernel matrices in tropical regions might affect kernels near the poles. The strength of such an effect might be an interesting question for future work

that could build up on the existing error metric. A tradeoff might be to group elements by regions before applying a truncated singular value decomposition.

5.2. Spatio-Temporal Analysis

For spatio-temporal analysis of water vapour isotopologues, we extracted pattern from the $\{H_2O, \delta D\}$ -space with respect to the spatio-temporal context. We approached this using the general-purpose density-based clustering algorithms DBSCAN and HDBSCAN. The comparison of the different cluster validation indexes as well as the visual validation reveal that HDBSCAN outperforms DBSCAN. But even if cluster validation indexes aim to give an objective and quantitative measure of clustering results, simple measures like the Davies-Bouldin Index and the Silhouette Index have limited validity for the given data: First, they do not take noise into account which tends to higher scores for many noise objects. Second, they are better suited for convex clusters which are not necessarily produced by density-based clustering algorithms. With DBCV a promising measure exists that is more consistent to the notion of density-based clustering, but the used implementation needs better performance to operate at large-scale.

Our clustering evaluation aimed to provide an objective estimate of the cluster quality by common cluster validation indexes. To show the true potential of spatio-temporal clustering in atmospheric science, more extended validations are needed. Especially the mapping between clusters and atmospheric processes requires further investigation. This might include a cross validation of clustered results with simulated atmospheric processes.

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A. Appendix

A.1. Error Estimation

A.1.1. Nitric Acid

Figure A.1.: Error estimation of HNO_3

Figure A.2.: Size of HNO_3

A.1.2. Greenhouse Gases

Figure A.3.: Error estimation of greenhouse gas CH_4

Figure A.4.: Error estimation of greenhouse gas N_2O

Figure A.5.: Size of greenhouse gases

A.1.3. Atmospheric Temperature

Figure A.6.: Error estimation of atmospheric temperature

Figure A.7.: Size of atmospheric temperature

A.2. Source Code and Related Data

The source code is publicly available at GitHub¹. The release 0.1.0 marks the status of the project at the stated period of the thesis. Detailed information about the setup and the usage are provided by `readme.md`. Further related data can be found with the Digital Object Identifier 10.5281/zenodo.3360021.

¹<https://github.com/weberandraseu/iasi>